

D33.2 Earth Science metadata, semantics and ontology harmonisation report

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Abstract:

This report contains the results of the harmonization analysis and the strategy to have harmonized metadata, ontologies and semantics in the Earth Science domain. For more see the Executive Summary that follows.

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Executive Summary

Earth science communities use various ontologies/schemas to describe different kinds of datasets and for different reasons, and there is not an integrated (harmonized) schema for describing all concepts of Earth science. The purpose of this deliverable is to summarize and analyze the results of the surveys conducted in WP15, identify the needs and gaps between communities based also on the results of the user requirements (WP12) and propose strategies for having harmonized metadata, semantics and ontologies.

The deliverable is organized in three main sections aiming at (a) analyzing the results of the WP15 survey, (b) inspecting how the needs of communities are fulfilled and identifying gaps based on the user requirements and (c) describing general approaches for harmonization/integration of information and how they fit into SCIDIP-ES (and in particular in WP33).

The first section is the analysis of the WP15 results. Particular focus is given in the part of the survey concerning metadata, semantics and ontologies. The objective is to perform an analysis of the semantic models that are widely used by different communities, in terms of their usability, adoption, configurability, extensibility across different Earth Science domains.

The second section uses the results of the user requirements analysis (WP12) as a pivot in order to identify if the aforementioned ontologies cover the needs of communities.

The results of the two previous sections are used for the definition of the strategies to have harmonized metadata, semantics and ontologies, able to satisfy the user needs coping with the different Earth Science domain approaches. For the definition of the strategy, core ontologies as well as extensions and mappings for the Earth Science domain have been investigated.

The results of this deliverable (the strategy) will be provided as input in T21.8 (Finding Aids Toolkit Development).

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1 Introduction (Purpose and Context)

1.1 Description of Task 33.2 (Harmonization of Earth Science metadata, semantics and ontologies)

As stated in the DoW:

This task will perform a deep analysis of Earth Science communities **needs and gaps** in terms of available **metadata, semantics and ontologies** starting from the user requirements collected in WP 12 and the results of the survey carried out in WP 15. The results of this analysis will be used to define the **most appropriate strategy to have harmonized metadata, semantics and ontologies** able to satisfy user needs coping with the different ES domains approaches. For instance, in this task we will investigate the available **core ontologies** for provenance, like CRM Digital which is the extension (for digital objects) of CIDOC CRM (ISO standard 21127), OPM (Open Provenance Model), as well as **extensions/mappings required** for the ES domain. The strategy could for example consist in the need for a **mediator** among existing ontologies and in such a case the **specifications will be defined in the task and provided as input to Task 21.8** for the implementation activities and for the validation in the ES specific domain.

1.2 Description of Deliverable D33.2 (Earth Science metadata, semantics and ontology harmonization report)

As stated in the DoW:

The report contains the results of the harmonization analysis and the strategy to have harmonized metadata, ontologies and semantics in the Earth Science domain.

1.3 Document Organisation

The document is organized as follows:

- Section 1 is the introductory section of the deliverable
- Section 2 contains an analysis of the Earth Science semantic models based on the results of the WP15 survey [1] and the user requirements report [2].
- Section 3 focuses on requirements and gaps as regards harmonization.
- Section 4 proposes a strategy towards the harmonization of metadata, semantics and ontologies
- Section 5 concludes and provides a summary

Extra information is given at the appendix of this deliverable. In particular:

- Annex A contains the bibliographic references
- Annex B contains the list of figures and tables
- Annex C contains a table with the terminology used in this deliverable
- Annex D contains some information and suggestions for the Finding Aids Toolkit

2 Analysis of the Main Earth Science Models

Taken from the DoW: “a deep analysis of Earth Science communities needs and gaps in terms of available metadata, semantics and ontologies starting from the user requirements collected in WP 12 and the results of the survey carried out in WP 15.”

At first we summarize the results of the **metadata/ontologies/semantics** survey [1] done in the context of Task 15.3. This survey focused on identifying the current status in terms of the available metadata, semantics and ontologies that are currently in use in the earth science community. Within this study several sources have been exploited (including online questionnaires, interviews, results from past and ongoing relevant projects, independent search activities, e.t.c.).

The survey activities yielded 44 distinct models, which we categorized according to their main role and broad domain (i.e. top level, Atmosphere, Biosphere, Geology/Geoinformatics, Cryosphere, Oceanography). As regards their purpose, their main use is for querying and exchanging data (only 20% of these models are used for natively storing data) and 60% of these models are available in XML. Most of these deal with metadata about Geology/Geoinformatics which is for capturing information about the solid earth and the study of the capture, qualification, classification, storage, processing and production of spatial information of earth.

The left path of Figure 1 shows the availability of these models in various **formats** (XML, UML, RDF/S, OWL, other). Most of these models (Approximately 60%) exist in XML format. The right part of Figure 1 shows the results regarding their **usage**. It follows that most of them are used for *querying* and *exchanging* data. Only about 20% are used for natively storing data.

Figure 1 Format and Actual Usage Information

In this section we concentrate on those semantic models (or groups of semantic models) that are mainly used by the partners of SCIDIP-ES. The following table shows for each model class the SCIDIP-ES partners who are using it, and if the model was provided through the questionnaire and/or directly by a SCIDIP-ES partner. These models are then further analysed in subsequent sections.

Semantic Model	Used by SCIDIP-ES partner	Is a Questionnaire response	Provided by SCIDIP-ES partner
ISO 19100	CNES, DLR, GIM, ISPRA, NERC, STFC	✓	✓
CF Conventions	INGV, STFC	✓	✓
CGI Vocabularies and Ontologies	ISPRA	✓	✓
OGC (including HMA)	CNES, DLR, ESA, JUB, STFC, GIM	✓	✓
CSML	STFC	✓	✓
GEMET	GIM, ISPRA, GEMET	✓	✓
MOIST	INGV	✓	
MOLES	STFC	✓	✓
OPEG	ESA, GIM	✓	✓
SWEET		✓	
THIST	ISPRA	✓	
CIDOC CRM	ESA, FORTH		✓
Dublin Core	ESA, INGV	✓	✓
VOID			✓
SKOS	NERC, UTV	✓	✓

Table 1 Semantic Models used by SCIDIP-ES partners

2.1 User Requirements Summary

In general we could identify two main requirements:

- Users need easy ways to discover information. There is hence a need for systems that facilitate integrated browsing/querying over all types of Earth Science (ES) resources. While a vast amount of information about ES can be found in various locations around the world, the comprehensive gathering, organisation, evaluation and dissemination of such information is a challenge.
- Data exploitation and utilization in and across different communities

More details about the needs and gaps are given in Section 3.

2.2 The “Big Picture” conceptually

The existing Earth Science resources can be found in a plethora of different forms (from research papers, databases, files, catalogues, etc). However we can make the following basic distinctions

- Core conceptualization of Earth Sciences
- Human Activities
- Products of Human Activities

Figure 2 The “Big Picture”

The above distinctions and the relationships between these models can be characterized by a core conceptual model of fundamental categories and their relationships. It is a kind of high level picture of the relationships between human activities and their targets, as they appear on the highest level of description of all scientific products and services. They are the ones necessary for the first level selecting relevant information, and for managing and maintaining the referential integrity of the most fundamental contextual information. It is only on a more specialized level that **all** the entities in these models are refined by specific, open-ended terminologies (typologies, taxonomies) and a relatively small set of more specific relationships among them.

Figure 3 Core Conceptual Backbone

The next step is to use the big picture presented in the previous section as a guide for identifying what the aforementioned semantic models cover. This will provide a top-down visualization of the current state of art of the semantic models that are currently in use in the Earth Science domain which is useful for interoperability purposes. In addition, this will enable the identification of overlaps and gaps.

2.3 Analysis of the Semantic Models and their Position in the “Big Picture”

In this section we will analyze in more detail the semantic models presented in the prologue of Section 2. For each model we will provide some domain-specific information. In particular we will specify how/where each model fits in the “Core Conceptual Backbone” (shown in Figure 3). This approach will allow us to identify possible gaps and overlaps between different semantic models.

2.3.1 ISO 19100 series

The International Organization for Standardization has established the ISO 19100 series for: (a) defining the basic semantics and structure of geographic information for data management and data interchange purposes and (b) defining geographic information service components and their behaviour for data processing purposes. These standards support data management,

acquiring, processing, analyzing, accessing and disseminating data between different users, systems and locations for geographic information¹.

Broadly this set of standards covers 5 different areas:

- The overarching **reference model** describes how all the different aspects in the series relate to each other.
- The **encoding area** concerns the methodology for storage, transfer and presentation of geographic data.
- The **data models** define the mathematical models for geometry, and the operators that work on them.
- The **data administration** defines metadata models, how to allow access to data via geospatial queries, and the overall quality control of datasets.
- The **profiling concept** introduces tools to select and combine a subset of the full series, and adapt this to specific needs of an application.

A more detailed description of each of the standards will follow:

Reference Model	
ISO Standard	Description
ISO 19101 - Reference model	<p>This International Standard provides a reference model for describing the overall requirements for standardization and the fundamental principles that apply in developing and using standards for geographic information. The Reference Model is divided according to two focus points:</p> <p>Domain Reference Model: this defines the semantics and structures needed for managing and interchanging geographic information. It provides schema's for datasets, their metadata and applications. It introduces the concept of a feature: an abstraction of a real-world phenomenon. Geographic features are those with a real-world location.</p> <p>Architecture Reference Model: this provides the structures needed by services that process/provide geographic datasets and metadata, and the interfaces needed to interoperability between them. It makes the distinction clear between these services and other IT services.</p>
ISO 19103 – Conceptual Schema Language	<p>This Technical Specification identifies the combination of the Unified Modeling Language (UML) static structure diagram with its associated Object Constraint Language (OCL) and a set of basic type definitions as the conceptual schema language for specification of geographic information. Actually, it specifies a profile of UML for use with geographic information and provides guidelines on how UML should be used to create standardized geographic information and service models.</p>

¹ Information concerning objects or phenomena that are directly or indirectly associated with a location relative to Earth

<p>ISO 19104 – Terminology</p>	<p>This International Standard provides the guidelines and criteria for the collections and maintenance of concepts to be used in a geographical terminology. It is based on principles for terminology writing defined in ISO 10241:1922 and ISO 704:2000.</p>
<p>ISO 19105 – Conformance and Testing</p>	<p>This standard provides the framework of an Abstract Test Suite, to test if a geographic product or services conforming to the ISO 19100 Standards. This is the only goal of the test suite as defined here: concepts like robustness and performance are not considered.</p>
<p>ISO 19106 – Profiles</p>	<p>This International Standard is intended to define the concept of a profile of the ISO geographic information standards developed by ISO/TC 211 and to provide guidance for the creation of such profiles.</p> <p>An ISO geographic profile is a subset of one or several standards from the ISO 19100 series (if necessary combined with other ISO standards), or including non-ISO geographic information standards in a less strict definition, that are applicable to a given product or service. For example, there may be a profile of ISO 19115 developed to serve a particular application area such as cadastral mapping. The profile would consist of a choice of the metadata elements available in ISO 19115. ISO 19115 would serve as a base standard for the development of the profile.</p> <p>A profile makes explicit any relationships that may exist within a set of base standards used together (relationships which can be implicit in the definitions of the base standards themselves), and may also specify particular details of each base standard being used. It may also refer to other profiles in order to reference functions and interfaces defined by them, and thus limit its own direct reference to base standards. The registration of profiles allows them to be explicitly referenced (normatively or informatively) within other profiles.</p> <p>Some base standards provide options allowing for a variety of applications. Base standards may also be combined in various ways in different applications. Profiles promote integration of base standards by defining how to use a combination of base standards for a given functional environment. Profiles do not contradict base standards, but may make choices where options and ranges of values are available.</p>

Table 2 The ISO 19100 series – Reference Model

<p>Data Models</p>	
<p>ISO Standard</p>	<p>Description</p>
<p>ISO 19107 – Spatial</p>	<p>This standard provides the taxonomy of topological and geometrical objects and operators. Geometry objects are concerned with the quantitative description of a feature: its size, location, dimension, etc. Topology objects are</p>

<p>Schema</p>	<p>concerned with a shape's invariant properties. These objects are commonly known as "vector data".</p> <p>Operators are used to manipulate and query these objects.</p>
<p>ISO 19108 – Temporal Schema</p>	<p>This standard defines the taxonomy of concepts necessary to describe the temporal characteristics of geographic data, such as the distinction between a Period and an Instant, and the temporal reference system (as defined in ISO 8601).</p>
<p>ISO 19109 – Rules for Application Schema</p>	<p>This International Standard defines rules for creating application schemas in a consistent manner (including the consistent definition of features) to facilitate the acquiring, processing, analysing, accessing, presenting and transferring of geographic data between different users, systems and locations.</p> <p>An application schema provides the formal description of the data structure and content required by one or more applications. An application schema contains the descriptions of both geographic data and other related data. A fundamental concept of geographic data is the feature.</p> <p>Geographic features are real world phenomena associated with a location relative to the Earth, about which data are collected, maintained, and disseminated. Geographic features occur at two levels: instances and types. At the instance level, a geographic feature is represented as a discrete phenomenon that is associated with its geographic and temporal coordinates and may be portrayed by a particular graphic symbol. These individual feature instances are grouped into classes with common characteristics: feature types. It is recognized that geographic information is subjectively perceived and that its content depends upon the needs of particular applications. The needs of particular applications determine the way instances are grouped into types within a particular classification scheme.</p>
<p>ISO 19110 – Methodology for Feature Cataloguing</p>	<p>This International Standard defines the methodology for cataloguing feature types. It specifies how the classification of feature types is organized into a feature catalogue and presented to the users of a set of geographic data. This International Standard is applicable to creating catalogues of feature types in previously un-catalogued domains and to revising existing feature catalogues to comply with standard practice.</p> <p>This International Standard is applicable to the definition of geographic features at the type level. It may be used as a basis for defining the universe of discourse being modelled in a particular application, or to standardize general aspects of real world features being modelled in more than one application.</p> <p>However, the full description of the contents and structure of a geographic dataset is given by the application schema developed in compliance with ISO 19109. The feature catalogue defines the meaning of the feature types and their associated feature attributes, feature operations and feature associations</p>

	contained in the application schema.
ISO 19111 – Spatial Referencing by Coordinates	This standard defines the conceptual schema for the description of spatial referencing by coordinates. Coordinates are numerically coded locations of a real-world location, usually ranging from one- to four-dimensional coordinates (three spatial coordinates and one temporal). Translating these coordinates to an actual location requires two systems: a datum and a coordinate system. A datum is a mathematical model to define points on a sphere. The coordinate system defines these points based on coordinates. This standard defines the use of datums and coordinate systems, which combine into coordinate reference systems.
ISO 19112 – Spatial Referencing by Geographic Identifiers	This standard defines the location of geographic features, not by the use of coordinates as in ISO 19111, but rather in relationship to other geographic features. It introduces the concept of a gazetteer, a directory of geographic identifiers describing location instances.

Table 3 The ISO-19100 series – Data Models

Geographic Information Management	
ISO Standard	Description
ISO 19113 – Quality Principles	This standard describes the principles for evaluating the quality of geographic data. The quality of a dataset quality is described with two components: using quality elements, which describe quantitatively a specific characteristic of a dataset (e.g. completeness, positional accuracy, etc.) and quality overview elements, which contain non-quantity information.
ISO 19114 – Quality Evaluation Procedures	This standard provides a framework of procedures to perform and report the quality evaluations as established in ISO 19113. It provides the option to perform different quality evaluations, depending on the need of a user of the dataset.
ISO 19115 – Metadata	The objective of this International Standard is to provide a structure for describing digital geographic data. It defines metadata elements, provides a schema and establishes a common set of metadata terminology, definitions, and extension procedures. It provides information about the identification, the extent, the quality, the spatial and temporal schema, spatial reference, and distribution of digital geographic data. This International Standard defines:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • mandatory and conditional metadata sections, metadata entities, and metadata elements • the minimum set of metadata required to serve the full range of metadata applications (data discovery, determining data fitness for use, data access, data transfer, and use of digital data) • optional metadata elements – to allow for a more extensive standard description of geographic data, if required • a method for extending metadata to fit specialized needs
<p>ISO 19115-2 – Metadata Part 2: Extensions for Imagery and Gridded data</p>	<p>While the ISO 19115 metadata model does provide some provisions for imagery and gridded data, the requirements were not fully developed at the time ISO 19115:2003 was drafted.</p> <p>This ISO 19115-2 extends the existing geographic metadata standard by defining the schema required for describing imagery and gridded data. It provides information about the properties of the measuring equipment used to acquire the data, the geometry of the measuring process employed by the equipment, and the production process used to digitize the raw data. This extension deals with metadata needed to describe the derivation of geographic information from raw data, including the properties of the measuring system, and the numerical methods and computational procedures used in the derivation. The metadata required to address coverage data in general is addressed sufficiently in the general part of ISO 19115.</p>
<p>ISO 19123 – Schema for Coverage Geometry and Functions</p>	<p>This International Standard defines a conceptual schema for the spatial characteristics of coverages. Coverages support mapping from a spatial, temporal or spatiotemporal domain to feature attribute values where feature attribute types are common to all geographic positions within the domain. A coverage domain consists of a collection of direct positions in a coordinate space that may be defined in terms of up to three spatial dimensions as well as a temporal dimension. Examples of coverages include rasters, triangulated irregular networks, point coverages and polygon coverages. Coverages are the prevailing data structures in a number of application areas, such as remote sensing, meteorology and mapping of bathymetry, elevation, soil and vegetation. This International Standard defines the relationship between the domain of coverage and an associated attribute range. The characteristics of the spatial domain are defined whereas the characteristics of the attribute range are not part of this standard.</p>
<p>ISO 19156 – Observations and Measurements</p>	<p>This International Standard defines a conceptual schema for observations, and for features involved in sampling when making observations. An observation is an act that results in the estimation of the value of a feature property using a designated procedure, such as a sensor, instrument, algorithm or process chain. An observation is associated with a discrete time instant or period through which a number, term or other symbol is assigned to a phenomenon. The result of an observation is an estimate of the value of a property of some feature, so the details of the observation are metadata concerning the value</p>

	of the feature property. Therefore ISO 19156 standard covers datasets acquired using both instruments/sensors or numerical models.
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Table 4 The ISO-19100 series – Geographic Information Management standards

Geographic Information Services	
ISO Standard	Description
ISO 19119 – Services	<p>This International Standards specifies the architecture for services that manipulate and distribute geographic data. It is an extension of the Architectural Reference Model (as defined in ISO 19101). The goal of this standard is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • enable interoperability between services • support the creation of a service catalogue • allow the separation of data instances and server instances • provide an abstract framework, without committing to a specific implementation <p>This standard presents geographic services taxonomy and a list of example geographic services planned in the services taxonomy. It prescribes how to create a platform-neutral service specification, and how to derive platform-specific service specifications that are conformant with this.</p>
ISO 19116 – Positioning Services	This standard specifies the data structure and content of services that unambiguously define the location of a device, covering a multitude of positioning systems.
ISO 19117 – Portrayal	It gives general guidelines to the application developers about the mechanism to be used to portray the feature instances of a dataset. It provides a framework for developers to create software that enables users to access and process geographic data from a variety of sources across a generic computing interface within an open information technology environment.
ISO 19125-1 - Simple Feature Access-Part 1: Common Architecture	This section of the two-part standard describes the common architecture of a simple feature geometry. It is an implementation of the (full) spatial schema of ISO 19107, both the features and the spatial operators, and introduces the concept of the Well-Known Text (WKT) and Well-Known-Binary (WKB), structured representations of a geographic feature aimed at humans and computers respectively. This allows for the interchange of features using an SQL client.
ISO 19125-2 - Simple Feature Access-Part	The second section of this standard implements the ISO 19107 spatial schema, following the common implementation of ISO 19125-1, into a standard Structured Query Language schema for use in databases.

1: SQL Option	
<p>ISO 19128 – Web Map Server Interface</p>	<p>The Web Map Server interface specifies the web interface to be used by services that generate pictorial renderings of maps. Software that enables this capability needs to understand the format in which the requests are given. For this reason the concept of Layers and Styles are introduced. These are used to transform vector or raster data into a graphical format (from which the original data cannot be retrieved).</p> <p>Two operations are required by this standard:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>GetCapabilities</i>, which returns a description of the data that the WMS can provide • <i>GetMap</i>, which returns an rendered image based on the given parameters <p>Optionally <i>GetFeatureInfo</i> may be implemented, which returns information about the feature data present at a particular location within the map.</p>

Table 5 The ISO-19100 series – Geographic Information Services standards

Encoding Rules	
ISO Standard	Description
<p>ISO 19118 – Encoding</p>	<p>This International Standard specifies the requirements for defining encoding rules to be used for the interchange of geographic data within ISO 19100 series. In particular it specifies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirements for creating encoding rules based on UML schemas • Requirements for creating encoding services • Requirements for XML-based encoding rules for neutral interchange of data <p>The goal of these encoding rules is to standardize the storage and transfer of geographic data, in a way that is humanly readable but mainly intended for computer use.</p>
<p>ISO 19136 – Geography Markup Language (GML)</p>	<p>This International Standard, which follows the encoding rules of ISO 19118, defines the XML extension Geography Markup Language (GML). GML is an XML grammar written in XML schema for the description of application schemas as well as the transport and storage of geographic information.</p> <p>The key concepts used by GML are drawn from the ISO 19100 and the OpenGIS Abstract Specification [29].</p> <p>It also contains the conceptual models defined in the following ISO 19100</p>

	<p>standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 19103 – Conceptual Schema Language (units of measure, basic types) • ISO 19107 – Spatial Schema (geometry and topology objects) • ISO 19108 – Temporal Schema (temporal geometry and topology objects, temporal reference systems) • ISO 19109 – Rules for Application schemas (features) • ISO 19111 – Spatial Referencing by coordinates (coordinate reference systems) • ISO 19123 – Schema for coverage geometry and functions
<p>ISO 19139 – XML Schema Implementation</p>	<p>The ISO 19115 standard describes the conceptual model for the description of metadata of datasets. It is however described using UML and does not provide an actual encoding.</p> <p>This encoding is provided in the ISO 19139 standard, using an XML schema implementation of the concepts in ISO 19115. It follows the requirements of creating encoding rules as laid out in ISO 19118.</p>

Table 6 The ISO-19100 series – Encoding Rules

There are many models that are related or based on one (or more) of the ISO 19100 series of standards.

- MOLES (Section 2.3.8) is such a model. In particular MOLES is defined using ISO 19101 (Reference Model), ISO 19106 (Profiles), ISO 19109 (Rules for Application Schema) standards as guidelines. It also includes concepts from different ISO 19100 series schemas.
- GEMET (Section 2.3.5) multilingual thesaurus is used quite often in conjunction with ISO 19100 series of standards. For example GEMET is used as a source of keywords when documenting metadata of geographic datasets, dataset series and services. When following the INSPIRE technical guidance for metadata, GEMET keywords are mandated to indicate the INSPIRE spatial data theme that the dataset belongs to.
- GeoSciML (Section 2.3.6) is fully based on the ISO series of standards. It develops a conceptual model of geoscientific information drawing on the ISO 19103 (Conceptual Schema Language). It implements a subset of this model in the ISO 19109 (Rules for Application Schema) and an XML/GML encoding of the model based on ISO 19136 (Geography Markup Language).

OGC (Section 2.3.2) and ISO are cooperating in the development of standards and cross adopt each other's standards when they have reached the required level of maturity. OGC has been responsible/ aiding in many aspects of the ISO 19100 series. Its reference model for Open Distributed Processing has been a conceptual basis for the ISO 19100 series of standards.

The importance of the ISO19XXX series of Standards for Geography has been boosted in the recent years through the adoption of the European Directive on an Infrastructure for Spatial Information (INSPIRE) [53] in Europe. The INSPIRE directive came into force on 15 May 2007 and will be implemented in various stages, with full implementation required by 2019. The INSPIRE directive aims to create a European Union (EU) spatial data infrastructure which will enable the sharing of environmental spatial information among public sector organisations and better facilitate public access to spatial information across Europe. A European Spatial Data Infrastructure will assist in policy-making across boundaries. Therefore the spatial information considered under the directive is extensive and includes a great variety of topical and technical themes.

INSPIRE is based on a number of common principles:

- Data should be collected only once and kept where it can be maintained most effectively.
- It should be possible to combine seamless spatial information from different sources across Europe and share it with many users and applications.
- It should be possible for information collected at one level/scale to be shared with all levels/scales; detailed for thorough investigations, general for strategic purposes.
- Geographic information needed for good governance at all levels should be readily and transparently available.
- Easy to find what geographic information is available, how it can be used to meet a particular need, and under which conditions it can be acquired and used.

The high-level INSPIRE directive is complemented by a number of Implementing Rules focussing on particular topics as metadata, view services, discovery services and data specifications. These Implementing Rules have legislative value and are accompanied by so-called Technical Guidances that are not legally mandated but describe recommended ways for implementing the Implementing Rules. The following (meta)data-models are described:

- The Implementing Rule for Metadata [54] describes a minimal set of metadata elements that are required for describing geographic datasets, dataset series and services. The associated technical guidance [55] explains how to implement this on the basis of the metadata models of ISO19115 and ISO19119 and encoded in ISO19139.
- The data specifications put forward a detailed data model for all the different Feature Types that are part of the 34 INSPIRE Spatial Data themes. These INSPIRE themes are divided over three Annexes of the Directive. The Annex that a data theme falls in determines the timeframe for harmonisation of the data with respect to the harmonised data model. The INSPIRE data specifications are fully grounded on the ISO19XXX series of models and the methodology for developing application schema. The INSPIRE data specifications comprise a large set of documents of which the interrelationship is sketched in the following Figure:

Figure 4 INSPIRE Data specifications overview

- D2.3: Definition of Annex Themes and scope [58]: defines the scope of each of the individual data themes
- D2.5: The Generic Conceptual Model [56] serves as the common foundation for all theme-specific INSPIRE data specifications. Every INSPIRE data specifications' applications schema shall import the definitions of this generic conceptual model. As the Generic Conceptual model is based on the harmonised model of the ISO19100 series of standards, these standards form the basis of each INSPIRE data specification.
- D2.6: Methodology for the development of the data specifications [57]: defines a predictable and repeatable process model for the development of the INSPIRE data specifications based on an iterative approach for incrementally growing INSPIREs' degree of definition and implementation. It defines the different process steps and the responsibilities for completing each step.
- D2.7: Guidelines for the encoding of spatial data [59]: defines the valid and default encoding rules for the INSPIRE data models. The default encoding rule is based on ISO19136- additional encodings may be specified for each application schema.
- D2.8: The data specifications themselves: one document per spatial data theme accompanied by the UML Model
- D2.9: O&M guidelines [60]: since many of the INSPIRE themes relate to "Observations", the O&M model is a logical base model to serve as a basis for the development of the data specifications. Since there are many ways for utilising the core constructs of O&M, guidelines are provided that specify how this standard is to be used within INSPIRE.

2.3.2 OGC Standards

The Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC) is an international industry consortium of 483 companies, government agencies and universities participating in a consensus process to develop publicly available interface standards. OGC Standards support interoperable solutions that "geo-enable" the Web, wireless and location-based services and mainstream IT. The standards empower technology developers to make complex spatial information and services accessible and useful with all kinds of applications.

The OGC Technical Committee (TC) has developed an architecture in support of its vision of geospatial technology and data interoperability called the OpenGIS Abstract Specification. The Abstract Specification provides the conceptual foundation for most OGC specification development activities. Open interfaces and protocols are built and referenced against the Abstract Specification, thus enabling interoperability between different brands and different kinds of spatial processing systems. The Abstract Specification provides a reference model for the development of OpenGIS Implementation Specifications. The Abstract Specification is broken into 16 Topics in order to assist development of different topics from different working groups. These topics are:

Topic 1 - Feature Geometry. The description of this Abstract Specification is identical to ISO 19107 (Section 2.3.1). In particular it specifies conceptual schemas for describing the spatial characteristics of geographic features. It also provides a set of spatial operations consistent with these schemas.

Topic 2 - Spatial Referencing by Coordinates. This Abstract Specification defines the conceptual schema for the description of spatial referencing by coordinates, optionally extended to spatio-temporal referencing. It describes the minimum data required to define one-, two- and three-dimensional spatial coordinate reference systems with an extension to merged spatial-temporal reference systems. It also allows additional descriptive information to be provided and also identifies the information required to change coordinates from one coordinate reference system to another.

Topic 3 - Locational Geometry Structures. This Abstract Specification provides the abstract models for technology that are used across the GIS landscape. In particular it provides the specification for the structures for the mapping of location systems. Its first heavy use is in support of Simple Feature geometry specification and their Spatial Reference Systems.

Topic 4 - Stored Functions and Interpolation. Information Systems apart from modelling geospatial information, they also build and present displays that are provide a human-friendly illustration of the relationships that are otherwise difficult to detect. We may, therefore, think of a coverage as a kind of display, as a kind of window with Cartesian coordinates. The abstract mathematical space of Cartesian coordinates for the window is called the Coverage Extent. Coverages require two stored functions for representing various information (e.g. temperature) corresponding to particular Earth coordinates.

Topic 5 - The OpenGIS Feature. "A Feature is an abstraction of a real world phenomenon"². If we associate it also with a location relative to Earth then it is called a

² Taken from the description of ISO-19101

geographic feature. Feature attributes describe measurable or describable phenomena about an object entity.

Topic 6 - The Coverage Type. According to [30] Coverages support mapping from a spatial, temporal or spatiotemporal domain to feature attribute values where feature attribute types are common to all geographic positions within the domain. A coverage domain consists of a collection of direct positions in a coordinate space that may be defined in terms of up to three spatial dimensions as well as a temporal dimension. Examples of coverages include rasters, triangulated irregular networks, point coverages and polygon coverages. This International Standard defines a conceptual schema for the spatial characteristics of coverages.

Topic 7 - Earth Imagery Case. This specification provides a description a reference model for the processing of geographic imagery. This model identifies the scope of the standardization activity being undertaken and the context in which it takes place.

Topic 8 - Relationships between Features. This specification identifies the relationships that exist between features (described in Topic 5), in the same sense that entities in the real world are related to others in various ways.

Topic 9 - Quality. This specification specifies the necessary extensions to describe the accuracy and quality of several objects (including *Feature, Geometry, Coverage*).

Topic 10 - Feature Collections. The purpose of this specification is to provide a definition of a Feature Collection. It is an abstract object consisting of Feature Instances, their Feature Schema and their Project Schema.

Topic 11 - Metadata. The description of this specification has been replaced with by ISO-19115 – *Metadata* (Section 2.3.1).

Topic 12 - The OpenGIS Service Architecture. The description of this specification is identical to ISO-19119-*Services* (Section 2.3.1). This specification provides a framework to access and process geospatial data from a variety of sources across generic computing interfaces within an open information technology environment. Examples of such services that are further defined in Implementation Specifications are:

- a. **OGC Web Services (OWS):** are defined using open non-proprietary Internet standards to establish standards for geospatial data.
- b. **Web Map Service (WMS):** supports the creation and display of map images
- c. **Web Feature Service (WFS):** retrieves or alters feature descriptions
- d. **Web Coverage Service (WCS):** provides access and processing on coverage objects.
- e. **Web Processing Service (WPS):** defines an interface that facilitates the publishing of geospatial processes and the discovery of and binding to those processes by clients. Processes include any algorithm, calculation or model that operates on spatially reference data.
- f. **Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW):** defines common interfaces to discover, browse and query metadata about data, services and other potential resources.
- g. **Web Coverage Processing Service (WCPS):** provides a raster query language based on coverage model for ad-hoc processing and filtering on raster coverages.
- h. **Sensor Web Enablement (SWE):** enable all types of Web and/or Internet-accessible sensors, instruments and imaging devices to be accessible and, where applicable, controllable via the Web.

- Topic 13 - Catalog Services.** This specification covers the Geospatial Information Access Services which are part of the Abstract Specification – Topic 12. In particular
- Topic 14 - Semantics and Information Communities.** This specification allows the definition of groups of people, which are called Information Communities and allows them to efficiently manage the semantics of their objects and data.
- Topic 15 - Image Exploitation Services.** This specification describes the categories of image exploitation services needed to support the use of images and related coverage types.
- Topic 16 - Image Coordinate Transformation Services.** This specification defines the concepts used in image coordinate conversion service. It is part of the specification that describes services for transforming image position coordinates to (and from) ground position coordinates.

Figure 5 depicts the relationships between different topics.

Figure 5 The OGC Abstract Specification Topics

The OGC Abstract Specification creates and documents a conceptual model to support the creation of Implementation Specifications. Implementation Specifications are unambiguous technology platform specifications for implementation of industry-standard, software application programming interfaces. Geospatial domain semantics defined in the Abstract Specification are to be consistent across multiple technology platforms as defined in Implementation Specifications. Atop the Abstract Specification members have developed and continue to develop a growing number of specifications, or standards to serve specific needs for interoperable location and geospatial technology.

Geospatial information is a ubiquitous element of almost all data. Geospatial location and time, which are integral to all aspects of the work in the OGC and OGC standards, are exploited as a unifying theme to better understand the context of most real and abstract phenomena. More are listed below:

- *Geometry and Topology*: Geometry provides the means for quantitative description of the spatial characteristics of features, including dimension, position, size, shape, and orientation. Topology is useful for characterizing relationships between geometric objects without concern for the size or exact shape of the objects. The definition of Feature Geometry is identical to ISO 19107- Spatial Schema.
- *Feature*: A feature is an abstraction of a real world phenomenon. A geographic feature is a feature associated with a location relative to the Earth. The OGC Approach to feature modeling follows the principles specified in ISO 19109 – Rules for Application Schema.
- *Coverage*: Coverage is a special feature type. The model associates spatio-temporal positions to data values. The data attributes of coverage vary across its spatio-temporal extent. It is identical to ISO 19123 – Schema for Coverage, Geometry and Functions.
- *GML*: Geography Markup Language (for short GML) is an XML grammar to express geographical features. GML serves as a modeling language for geographic systems as well as an open interchange format for geographic transactions on the Internet. The GML information model is based on the ISO 19100 series and the OGC Abstract Specification.
- *GML Coverage*: It is based on the Geography Markup Language (GML) 3.2, an XML grammar written in XML Schema for the description of application schemas as well as the transport and storage of geographic information.
- *SWE*: a set of interfaces and protocols that enable a “Sensor Web” through which applications and services will be able to access sensors of all types over the Web.
- *Observations and Measurements*: It defines measurements and the relationships between them, mainly to improve the ability of software systems to discover and use data produced by measuring systems. Observations are modelled as Features within the context of ISO 19101 – Reference Model and ISO 19109 – Rules for Application Schema.
- *SensorML*: It specifies models and XML encoding for the core SensorML, as well as the definition of several SWE Common data components utilized throughout the SWE framework. Within SensorML, all processes and components are encoded as application schema of the Feature model in the Geographic Markup Language (GML) version 3.1.1.
- *TML*: Transducer Markup Language (TML) works within transducer exchange messages from multiple application domains (defence, weather, exploration, environmental, medical, industrial, security, etc.).
- *GeoDRM and GeoXACML*: It defines a conceptual model for digital rights management of geospatial resources.

Within the Earth Observation domain, ESA has been piloting a series of standardisation projects under the “Heterogeneous Missions Accessibility- HMA” banner to develop **specific profiles of OGC standards** optimised for dealing with Earth Observation data. The other European Space agencies such as CNES, DLR, EUMETSAT, ASI as well as the Canadian Space agency participate in this standardisation exercise. The aim of HMA is to standardise the

ground segment interfaces of the satellite missions, national and GMES Sentinels ones to allow easier access to Earth Observation data. HMA defines the interoperability concept and provide standards for coordinated data access enabling the interactions with services or Value Adders and EO Contributing Missions. The focus is oriented on the definition of the interfaces among the EO data Users and the different ground segments and between the ground segments in a well specified end to end architecture. Starting from the existing standards, when available, HMA, working side by side with the EC INSPIRE working group, has defined discovery, catalogue ordering feasibility analysis and identity management interface standards allowing collaboration among the space agencies. Further information on HMA can be found in the HMA Cookbook [[50].

Within the HMA series of projects several metadata models were developed:

- The metadata of EO dataset series (collections) is described by means of ISO 19115 which comprises the ISO metadata standard for geographic information belonging to the series of ISO 191xx standards. ISO 19115 provides information on the identification, extent, quality, spatial and temporal schemas, spatial reference and distribution of digital geographic data. The minimum metadata elements that need to be provided for an EO Product Collection is a superset of the elements mandated by the INSPIRE metadata regulation. The Minimal EO Product collection metadata is identified in the OGC EO Product Collection, Service and Sensor Discovery using the CS-W ebRIM Catalogue Best Practice Document [51].
- The minimal metadata for EO Related services adhering to the HMA EO profiles of the Web Map, Web Coverage, Ordering, Catalogue, Sensor Planning services are documented in [51] and based on ISO19119 in ISO 19139 encoding adhering to the minimum requirements set forward by the INSPIRE metadata regulation.
- The EO Product metadata is described using the Earth Observation Metadata Profile of Observations and Measurements [52]. In the frame of the initial Heterogeneous Missions Accessibility -Interoperability (HMA-I) project, ESA together with other GMES participating agencies as ASI, CNES, CSA-MDA, and DLR decided to model the metadata for Earth Observation products as geographic features encoded in the OGC Geographic Markup Language. The reasoning for adopting GML instead of a more traditional approach using the ISO19115 Geographic Information Metadata model was the fact that the ISO 19115 elements are more suited for describing the metadata of collections of EO Products rather than for describing individual EO products themselves. Indeed, typical mandatory ISO 19115 metadata elements like contact Information, citation, abstract, etc. constitute information that will be identical for each individual product in the collection. The complexity of the overall ISO19115 model with deep nesting of elements leads to a less efficient data structure for web access. In addition, a large number of specific metadata elements like for instance cloud cover are required to allow for efficient discovery of EO products that would need to be defined in a HMA specific extension to ISO19115. Instead of choosing this ISO19115 approach, it was agreed to model EO Product metadata as a geographic feature characterised by a footprint and a set of attributes. The encoding language for describing geographic features is the Geography Markup Language as standardised by the OGC and further adopted as ISO19136. The GML application schema for Earth Observation Products was developed during a consensus process in which a mapping was done between metadata elements from the different partners on to a

harmonised set of elements. Where possible, the element names were taken from corresponding element names within the ISO19115 and ISO19115 Part 2 standards. The EO Product Metadata was initially modelled as features (extending *<gml:AbstractFeature>*) and later on refined as *gml:observations*. The metadata elements common to all Earth Observation products were defined within an Earth Observation Product (EOP) GML application schema. Specific metadata elements for optical radar, atmospheric, altimetry, limb looking and synthesis and systematic products, were assigned to specific application schemas deriving from the base EOP schema. For products of specific missions requiring further metadata elements for their descriptions, it is possible to define a specific application schema deriving from one of the thematic application schemas.

Figure 6: EO Product Metadata profile of Observations and Measurements.

Since *GML:observation* became deprecated in favour of the Observations and Measurements information model, the latest revision of the EO Product metadata standard is using the O&M as the base information model. When migrating from *gml:observation* to O&M, also the Model-driven approach was applied for deriving the GML application schema. In this approach depicted in Figure 7, a universe of discourse is modelled formally as a conceptual model in a UML application schema using the General Feature Model of ISO 19109. Feature types may be registered in a feature catalogue specified within ISO 19110 for re-use (e.g. as part of other application schemas, through association or generalisation), thus aiding interoperability. From the UML model, a canonical XML encoding may be generated automatically, providing a GML application schema as per ISO19136. Exchange datasets containing feature instances may then be transformed from existing (legacy) database or other storage into an XML document conforming to the GML application schema.

Figure 7 Applying the Model-driven approach of ISO TC211

2.3.3 CGI Vocabularies

The development of CGI (Commission for the Management and Application of Geoscience Information) vocabularies follows on from the Multi-Lingual Thesaurus Working group, and Concept Definition Task Group aimed at developing concept vocabularies for populating GeoSciML interchange documents. The efforts of these two earlier groups have been merged into the Geoscience Terminology Working Group which is developing a portfolio of CGI Geoscience information vocabularies. There are currently 31 vocabularies in the CGI portfolio, which have been developed for the GeoSciML interchange documents. Considerable work is still required to create a further 30 vocabularies for GeoSciML (version 3), and 38 proposed vocabularies for use with EarthResourceML.

CGI Vocabularies are connected to several other models. These are:

- **SKOS** (Section 2.3.11): Whenever a CGI vocabulary is complete and mature it is migrated according to SKOS concepts, which will allow the production of a file in RDF/XML format.
- **GEMET** (Section 2.3.5): A MTG³/CGI concept has a `skos:exactMatch` to a GEMET concept. Although to implement this concept mapping (and the SWEET mapping described below) further work needs to be done to integrate multilingual Geoscience terms developed by the MLT Working Group with existing CGI vocabularies to provide multilingual support, and to make the thesaurus compiled by the MLT Working Group accessible online. The objective is to publish MTG/CGI concepts as RDF/XML through CGI vocabulary services, including asserted relationships between concepts in those vocabularies and concepts in other vocabularies.
- **SWEET**: A MTG/CGI concept is related to a SWEET concept through the `skos:closeMatch` property.
- **GeoSciML** (Section 2.3.6): CGI vocabulary terms are used to maintain semantic interoperability between a number of the concepts represented within GeoSciML,

³ Multilingual Thesaurus of Geosciences

although there are still 30 vocabularies required to fully represent GeoSciML version 3. In fact much of the current use of the CGI vocabularies seems to be to support GeoSciML

2.3.4 CF Conventions

The Climate and Forecast (CF) metadata conventions are designed to promote the processing and sharing of data files. In particular they are focused on the description of Earth sciences data. The data files are created with respect to the NetCDF API. The metadata defined by the CF conventions are included in same file with the data, thus making the file “self-describing”. CF conventions are intended for use with climate and forecast–related data.

NetCDF is a set of software libraries and self-describing, machine-independent data formats that support the creation, access, and sharing of array-oriented scientific data. The advantages of NetCDF are:

- **Self-Describing:** A NetCDF file contains information about the data and the metadata in a single file.
- **Portable:** It provides a platform-independent way to create/access NetCDF files.
- **Direct access:** A small subset of a large dataset may be accessed efficiently, without first reading through all the preceding data.
- **Appendable:** Data may be appended to a properly structured NetCDF file without copying the dataset or redefining its structure.
- **Sharable:** One writer and multiple readers may simultaneously access the same NetCDF file.
- **Archivable:** Access to all earlier forms of NetCDF data will be supported by current and future versions of the software.

NetCDF is standardized format from NASA and relatively recently standardized by the OGC[61]. The NetCDF library has been implemented in C programming language. NetCDF and the libraries based on it (in particular Fortran 77 and Fortran 90, C++, and all third-party libraries) can, starting from version 4.1.1, read some data in other data formats. Data in the HDF5 format can be read, with some restrictions, while data in the HDF4 format can be read by the NetCDF library if created using the HDF4 Scientific Data (SD) API. The Common Data Model has three layers, which build on top of each other to add successively richer semantics:

- The data access layer, also known as the syntactic layer, handles data reading.
- The coordinate system layer identifies the coordinates of the data arrays. Coordinates are a completely general concept for scientific data; specialized georeferencing coordinate systems, important to the Earth Science community, are specially annotated.
- The scientific data type layer identifies specific types of data, such as grids, images, and point data, and adds specialized methods for each kind of data.

2.3.5 GEMET

The General Environmental Multi-lingual Thesaurus (for short GEMET) has been developed as an indexing, retrieval and control tool for the European Topic Centre on Catalogue of Data Sources (ETC/CDS) and the European Environment Agency (EEA). The basic idea for its development was to merge the best available multilingual thesauri. GEMET was conceived as a general thesaurus thus specific thesaurus and descriptor systems were not included in its development and only their upper level structure and terminology was taken into account. Semantic equivalence across languages was guaranteed by review from a network of National Focal Points.

GEMET is one of the most widely used thesauri for supporting data discovery in Spatial Data Infrastructures (SDI). The INSPIRE Implementing Rule for Metadata requires that “at least one keyword shall be provided from GEMET” making it a standard for geo-spatial data discovery at European level. The current version is available in 22 languages, and contains over 6,000 descriptors. GEMET is publicly available in several formats. It can be browsed and searched on-line, accessed through Web services using XML (RDF/SKOS), HTTP and XML/RPC, or downloaded as HTML, RDF or SKOS files.

GEMET has several relationships with other models. It has multiple levels of connections with other thesauri either because they map their own terms on the GEMET ones, or they include GEMET in their own domain or they were included in GEMET.

Currently there is a mapping between GEMET and United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) AGROVOC thesaurus⁴, as well as one mapping with the United States National Agricultural Library (NAL) Agricultural thesaurus⁵.

The INSPIRE Metadata implementing rule requiring at least one keyword of each dataset/service to be a GEMET term creates a relationship with the INSPIRE Metadata derived from ISO 19115 specification.

In terms of its representation it is directly connected to RDF or SKOS data formats.

2.3.6 GeoSciML

GeoSciML⁶ was developed by CGI, the Commission for the Management and Application of Geoscience Information, a Commission of the International Union of Geological Sciences, as a Geography Markup Language (GML) derived schema to represent geology data. GeoSciML is a data interchange format which not strictly falls in the ontology/metadata/vocabulary domain. However, GeoSciML is built on a generic conceptual model that data providers should adopt in their internal representation of data to correctly provide GeoSciML formatted information. Being a domain – specific data interchange language GeoSciML defines a set of standardized entities, properties and relationships between them. For example an objects such as ‘faults’ has a ‘displacement’ property and has a relationship with the entity ‘Geologic Structure’ (‘faults are a type of Geologic Structure’). In order to enforce semantic interoperability, individual entities

⁴ <http://aims.fao.org/website/AGROVOC-Thesaurus/sub>

⁵ <http://agclass.nal.usda.gov/>

⁶ <http://www.geosciml.org/>

are defined through a set of standardized vocabularies. Some of these vocabularies are maintained by the CGI while others are maintained by delegated authorities, such as individual geological surveys. GeoSciML provides also the means to integrate user specific vocabularies in it. GeoSciML is used by the OneGeology⁷ project aiming at providing a worldwide geological map by harmonizing data from different providers.

GeoSciML is connected to other derived project aimed at more specific area of knowledge within the geosciences. It is also connected with the GML data specification and in general with vocabularies based on urn naming conventions.

The INSPIRE data specification for the Geology theme [62], recommends the use of GeoSciML as extension to the INSPIRE Geology Application schema to cover more detailed and/or use case specific geological information spatial object types and data types.

2.3.7 OTEG

OTEG has been developed within the framework of ESA activities in the field and in line with related past and ongoing projects. One such project is "Open Access Ontology / Terminology for the GMES⁸ Space Component" (OTEG) which aims at:

- Enlarging and spreading the use of EO satellite data
- Identifying relevant / useful EO data for users belonging to different application domains (non-EO)

The aim of the OTEG project is to help application experts in identifying relevant EO products, allowing them to easily identify the EO missions, sensors and products useful for their activity, using familiar semantic terms (i.e., terms pertaining to their application domain).

A GSCDA⁹ Semantics has been developed, containing all the knowledge needed to help the end users finding the relevant EO products. The GSCDA Semantics is actually a collection of ontologies and terminologies. The ontologies (the Multi-Domain Thesaurus, the GSCDA Taxonomy, and the mapping between the Multi-Domain Thesaurus and the GSCDA Taxonomy) have been implemented as three OWL files. The terminologies (the Multi-Domain Vocabulary and the GSCDA Vocabulary) have been implemented as two Excel files.

A software system has been developed in order to give the end users an easy way to exploit the knowledge expressed in the GSCDA Semantics. The system is composed of two web services and three web applications by means of the application experts will be helped in identifying relevant EO resources like EO products easily identifiable with the EO missions, sensors or products.

OTEG has several direct relationships with GEMET. Particularly it has multiple connections with GEMET elements integrating them without a specific global import of the GEMET ontology.

⁷ <http://www.onegeology.org/>

⁸ Global Monitoring for Environment and Security

⁹ GMES Space Component Data Access

Furthermore there is an OTEG info-domain file devoted to explain the origin of every OTEG concept, describing the source and the meaning of all elements.

2.3.8 MOLES

The MOLES (Metadata Object for Linking Environmental Sources) is an information model for describing metadata covering a broad range of applications within multiple disciplines. These are mainly, but not limited, those within the earth and physical sciences. MOLES is primarily of use to consumers of data, especially in an interdisciplinary context. It allows them to establish details of provenance, and to compare and contrast such information without recourse to discipline-specific metadata or private communications with the original investigators. MOLES can also be of use to the custodians of data, providing an organising paradigm for the data and metadata (which is how it is being deployed in the Centre for Environmental Data Archival, CEDA).

A typical sequence of data capturing involves one or more projects/activities under which a number of actions are undertaken, using appropriate tools and methods to produce the datasets. MOLES is not particularly concerned with the details of the datasets structures but is aimed at capturing the important provenance elements associated with them. Key components of MOLES include: Project descriptions; the action itself and the processes used to acquire or generate the data; the collection of data into groups according to user requirements.

The general structure of the model gives a central place to the concept of “observation”. An observation is regarded an act that results in the estimation of the value of a feature property using a designated procedure, such as a sensor, instrument, algorithm or process chain. An observation is associated with a discrete time instant or period through which a number, term or other symbol is assigned to a phenomenon. The result of an observation is an estimate of the value of a property of some feature, so the details of the observation are metadata concerning the value of the feature property.

MOLES is built entirely on ISO 19100 series geographic information standards, particularly the ISO 19156 Observations and Measurements standard (i.e. the base standard). In particular, it has been created:

1. following the guidance provided by ISO/TC 211 (i.e. ISO 19101, 19106 and 19109) and has been formalised in the Unified Modelling Language (UML) ISO/IEC 19501, following the guidance of ISO/TS 19103;
2. by integrating (i.e., either exploiting existing concepts and relationships or specialising the information in these standards) reusable modules of conceptual schemas defined within ISO 19100 series e.g. temporal schema , metadata ,etc.

2.3.9 ThIST

ThIST¹⁰ is an abbreviation of “*Thesaurus Italiano di Scienze della Terra*”, otherwise “*Italian Thesaurus of Earth Science*”. It is a thesaurus developed at ISPRA which is used to classify earth science related documentation and cartography within the internal library archives. It contains 10350 descriptors linked to each other through a set of 103,854 relationships of hierarchical, associative and equivalence types. ThIST is a bilingual thesaurus providing English equivalent of each descriptor. Descriptors are generally nouns with substantive significance. Adjectives, verbs and adverbs have been excluded from the thesaurus body in compliance with the norm ISO 2788. ThIST based search capabilities are provided on the metadata catalogue maintained by the Geological Survey at ISPRA.

2.3.10 VoID

The Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets (VoID)¹¹ is a vocabulary exclusively focused on providing metadata for describing datasets as a whole. It provides terms and patterns for describing RDF datasets, and is intended as a bridge between the publishers and users of RDF data. VoID descriptions can be used in many situations, ranging from data discovery to cataloguing and archiving of datasets, but most importantly it helps users find the right data for their tasks.

The contribution of VoID to representation and sharing of datasets is organized around four main areas of interest:

1. General Metadata (representation of core characteristics of a dataset and declaration of the dataset itself)
2. Access Metadata (provides information for accessing the dataset’s content)
3. Structural Metadata (any kind on information which can be used to understand the organization of a Dataset, and thus how to query its content)
4. Description of links between datasets (to relate different datasets together)

Thus, the VoID vocabulary provides a first pair of classes for describing datasets:

void:Dataset a resource representing a set of triples which have some sort of logical/physical homogeneity

void:Linkset a subclass of the above, datasets classified as *void:Linkset(s)* qualify their content as the description of links between different datasets.

Dublin Core then plays again an important (and thus reused inside VoID) role, as it is being adopted for covering most of the General Metadata about Interlinked Datasets. VOAF is based on the VoID standard and extends it to cover specifically ontology vocabularies. VOAF¹² though is not a standard promoted by W3C, it is widely used since it represents properties for publishing, linking and thus advertising vocabularies on the web.

¹⁰ http://www.isprambiente.gov.it/contentfiles/00003600/3687-thist.pdf/at_download/file

¹¹ <http://www.w3.org/TR/void/>

¹² <http://labs.mondeca.com/vocab/voaf/index.html>

2.3.11 SKOS

SKOS (abbreviation of Simple Knowledge Organization System) is implemented as a series of specifications and standards to support the use of Knowledge Organisation Systems, such as thesauri, classification schemes, and taxonomies, and other similar types of controlled vocabularies, within the framework of the semantic web. As an application of the Resource Description Framework (RDF), SKOS allows concepts to be composed and published on the World Wide Web, linked with data on the web and integrated into other concept systems.

SKOS is a common data model for sharing and linking knowledge organization systems via the Web. Many knowledge organization systems, such as thesauri, taxonomies, classification schemes and subject heading systems, share a similar structure, and are used in similar applications. SKOS captures much of this similarity and makes it explicit, to enable data and technology sharing across diverse applications. Because SKOS is based on RDF these representations are machine-readable and can be exchanged between software applications and published on the World Wide Web.

The SKOS data model provides a standard, low-cost migration path for porting existing knowledge organization systems to the Semantic Web. SKOS also provides a lightweight, intuitive language for developing and sharing new knowledge organization systems. It may be used on its own, or in combination with formal knowledge representation languages such as the Web Ontology Language (OWL).

It is very common to see SKOS adopted in domains such as agriculture, earth observation, biology, chemistry and others, as it allows for the systematization of concepts of a domain, when no strict formal semantics are required. It is useful to represent thesauri, concept schemes, vocabularies etc.

SKOS-XL is an extension to SKOS for reifying lexical entries. eXtended Labels (this is where the XL in the name of this vocabulary extension comes from) are RDF resources on their own (URIs or bnodes¹³, depending on the modeller's choice), with their lexical nature being delegated to one of their properties, called "*skosxl:lexicalForm*". This further indirection, which substantially is required to make labels become first-class-citizens in the modelled domain, allows for the specification of lexical properties linking labels between them, with no involvement of the concepts these are referencing.

SKOS allows CGI and other conceptual vocabularies to be ported to a shared space, based on a simplified model, enabling wider re-use and better interoperability. For example SKOS can be used to represent CGI vocabularies, and allow them to be exported to an RDF/XML file. SKOS would also provide a means of representing the relationships between ontology terms in for example the OTEG ontology and related thesauri in a machine readable manner. SKOS also has an application in mapping between concepts in different ontologies and vocabularies. For example, it appears also (from a Google search) that SKOS has been used to perform a mapping between concepts in the GEMET and OTEG ontologies.

¹³ Blank Nodes

2.3.12 Dublin Core

The Dublin Core metadata terms are a set of vocabulary terms which can be used to describe resources for the purposes of discovery. Typically, the Dublin Core vocabulary has been adopted and/or extended by many other domain vocabularies (e.g. the Bibliographic Ontology¹⁴) to directly refer to the domain objects represented in RDF (thus for describing data, e.g. the *dc:date* of a book is the date of publication of a book) though, as its properties can be connected to any *rdfs:Resource*, Dublin Core is also used by specific metadata vocabularies for describing RDF vocabularies and RDF Datasets, thus to provide overall information about data collections as a whole. The Abstract Model of Dublin Core [31] provides a specification of the components that are used in Dublin Core, and how these are connected to form more complex information structures.

Dublin Core is being used (even partially) in a vast quantity of vocabularies and datasets in the RDF world. Among the reported models, DC is being adopted (at least) inside VOID, VOAF and CIDOC/CRM.

2.3.13 ISO 21127

CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (ISO 21127) [3] is a formal ontology of 80 classes and 132 relations describing the underlying semantics of over a hundred database schemata and structures from all museum disciplines, archives and libraries. The primary role of CIDOC CRM is to enable information exchange and integration between heterogeneous sources on cultural heritage information. It defines (and is restricted to) the underlying semantics of database schemata and document structures used in cultural heritage and museum documentation in terms of a formal ontology. It does not define any of the terminology appearing typically as data in the respective data structures.

CIDOC CRM is the result of long-term interdisciplinary work and agreement. It has been derived by integrating (in a bottom-up manner) hundreds of metadata schemas and is stable (almost no change the last 10 years). We could say that the basic design principles are (a) empirical bottom-up knowledge engineering and (b) object-oriented modeling. As regards the latter, CIDOC CRM has a rich structure of “intermediate” classes and relations, which apart from being very useful for building query services (enabling queries at various levels of abstraction and granularity), it makes its extension to other domains easier and reduces the risk of over-generalization/specialization. In essence, it is a generic model for recording the “what has happened” in human scale. It can generate huge, meaningful networks of knowledge by a simple abstraction: history as meetings of people, things and information. On top of CIDOC CRM an extension has been built able to capture the modeling and the query requirements regarding the provenance of digital objects [23]. Recent projects (Ingeoclouds¹⁵, Cultural Geosemantics) successfully apply the CIDOC CRM to the integration of earth-science related content and developed extensions for scientific observations and geospatial data encoded in OGC standards.

¹⁴ BIBO <http://bibliontology.com>

¹⁵ <http://www.ingeoclouds.eu/>

2.3.14 Other Models / Systems

2.3.14.1 MOIST

MOIST¹⁶ is an abbreviation of Multidisciplinary Oceanic Information System aims at hosting big amounts of data and metadata coming from different disciplines. The system is consisted of a harvester engine that ingests and index data. The core part of the e-infrastructure is based on a relation database and its front-end exposes an API that allows data mining and retrieval.

MOIST is developed to adopt the most common standards (e.g. OGC, NASA, INSPIRE) for organising its information system.

2.3.15 Other Models for Representing Provenance Information

Several models have been proposed and are used for modelling and exchanging *provenance* information. The list includes, CIDOC CRM, Open Provenance Model (OPM), Provenir ontology, Provenance Vocabulary, Proof Markup Language, Dublin Core, PREMIS, WOT Schema, SWAN, Provenance Ontology, Semantic Web Publishing Vocabulary, Changeset Vocabulary. There are also various related W3C initiatives¹⁷.

2.4 An Overview of the Above Models

This sections aims at providing an overview of the aforementioned models.

At first we include *two* word clouds produced from the text of the above models (as described in the previous subsections). They are shown in the following figures.

¹⁶ <http://moist.rm.ingv.it>

¹⁷ http://www.w3.org/2011/prov/wiki/Main_Page

Core Conceptual Backbone (Figure 3), are to lesser or larger extent covered by the ISO 19100 series of standards. Just indicatively the concept of *services* is covered by ISO19109 (Service Architecture), ISO19128 (WMSI) and ISO 19142 (WFS) Standards, *mathematical models* are described in ISO 19107 (Spatial Schema) and ISO 19108 (Temporal Schema) Standards, metadata are covered by ISO 19115 (Metadata), ISO 19110 (Methodology for Feature Cataloguing) and ISO 19139 (Metadata – XML Schema Implementation) Standards.

The **OGC Suite Specifications** are tightly linked to the ISO standards. The **OGC Abstract Specifications** are based on the ISO set of standards and are intended to define a conceptual model for representing geographic features, sufficient enough to allow the description of software and system design related to real world situations, capturing the requirements and domain knowledge, capture design decisions, etc. This is complemented by the implementing specifications that define precise service interfaces and encodings. For that reason we could say that the scope of this set of standards encompasses most of the concepts discovered in the Core Conceptual backbone, however for some of them (e.g. Species) it does not provide any specific conceptual model/schema although such schema could easily be developed as extended application schema basing themselves on the core models.

The **CGI vocabularies** provide a means of implementing semantic interoperability, particularly between the concept definitions within GeoSciML, they are thus very relevant to implementing such concepts in databases. Because the vocabularies implement GeoSciML concepts they are relevant to a number of types of geological information (e.g. Samples, Species, etc.)

As a thesaurus, **GEMET** provides a relatively high level description of the concepts related to the environment. In the map GEMET finds it places among the services being commonly used to provide search services. It is also used as a global index for database and for publication classification since it defines relationships between terms and in this context is used to enhance keyword search capabilities.

The **GeoSciML** domain overlaps with much of the concepts found in the core conceptual model. In particular GeoSciML is adequate for describing Samples, Collections, Complex Systems, Types, Species and more.

OTEG domain overlaps with much of the Core Conceptual backbone. In particular it describes Samples, Collections, Observation, Types etc. and it is also used in discovery services. As a Multi-thesaurus, OTEG provides descriptions of the concepts related to the EO environment. In the map, shown in the figure below, OTEG finds its place among the services being commonly used to provide search services. It is also used as a global index for databases since it defines relationships between terms and in this context is used to enhance keyword search capabilities.

MOLES has been built on ISO 19100 series and in particular the ISO 19156 Observation and Measurements. It is relevant to almost all the entities illustrated in the Core Conceptual backbone, however it does not cover some concepts (e.g. Species).

ThIST is a multilingual thesaurus and represents mainly an indexing system and it is also used to provide discovery services.

As a vocabulary assisting the linkage of datasets, **Void** contributes to the creation of global indices of datasets, thus enabling discovery and even supporting vocabulary/data mediation activities.

CIDOC CRM (ISO 21127) and its extensions provide a variety of concepts useful for the description of multimedia information, digital objects and their provenance (*CRM_{dig}*) etc. The current version of CIDOC CRM contains the appropriate concepts for covering almost all the concepts found in the core conceptual model.

SKOS is a model for representing structured controlled vocabularies. As such it is applicable to a wide range of the concepts found in the core conceptual model, for expressing the basic structure and contents of concept schemes.

Dublin Core is a general metadata vocabulary which provides the basic attributes for describing simple (and some more complex) objects. It is used as a general metadata vocabulary used in a huge number of vocabularies and datasets in the linked data world.

Figure 10 illustrates the placement of each model using dashed boundaries.

Placement of the model	Comment
<h3 style="text-align: center;">OGC Specifications Placement</h3>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Geographic Data</p>
<h3 style="text-align: center;">CGI Vocabularies Placement</h3>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Geologic Information</p>

Placement of the model	Comment
<h3 style="text-align: center;">CF Conventions Placement</h3>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Climate and Forecast</p>
<h3 style="text-align: center;">CGI Vocabularies Placement</h3>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Environment</p>

Placement of the model	Comment
<h3 style="text-align: center;">GeoSciML Placement</h3> <p>The diagram illustrates the placement of GeoSciML within a broader scientific data infrastructure. It features several interconnected components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Left side (Information/Tools): Includes 'global indices', 'databases', 'Publications', 'mathem. Models', 'Records', and 'Forecasts'. A central purple oval labeled 'create maintain' is connected to 'Publications', 'mathem. Models', 'Records', and 'Forecasts'. 'Publications' also connects to 'databases', which in turn connects to 'global indices' and 'services'. Top center (Concepts): 'Molecular world and parts' leads to 'Species (bio,geo)'. 'Species' has a 'cross reference' loop and is connected to 'Observations'. Right side (Data/Context): A dashed box encloses 'collections', 'Samples or Specimen', 'Complex System', 'Time', 'Place', and 'Situation'. 'Samples or Specimen' is 'part of' 'collections' and 'from' 'Complex System'. 'Complex System' is 'from' 'Samples or Specimen' and 'occurs in' 'Time' and 'Place'. 'Situation' is 'based on' 'Simulation' and 'describe' 'Forecasts'. Central Hub: 'Activities' is connected to 'Observations', 'Simulation', 'Time', and 'Place'. 'Observations' and 'Simulation' are both connected to 'Activities'. Other Connections: 'Species' 'exemplifies' 'Samples or Specimen'. 'Molecular world and parts' 'exemplifies' 'Complex System'. 'Species' 'use to appear in' 'Molecular world and parts'. 'Observations' 'describe' 'Simulation'. 'Simulation' 'based on' 'Situation'. 'Complex System' 'occurs in' 'Situation'. </p>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Geographic Samples and Collections</p>
<h3 style="text-align: center;">OTEG Placement</h3> <p>The diagram is identical to the GeoSciML Placement diagram above, showing the same network of relationships between scientific entities and data infrastructure components. The focus, however, is on a different set of elements as indicated in the comment.</p>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Collections, Observations</p>

Placement of the model	Comment
<h3 style="text-align: center;">MOLES Placement</h3> <p>The diagram illustrates the MOLES Placement. It features a central 'Species (bio,geo)' box with a dashed box around it labeled 'cross reference'. 'Species (bio,geo)' is connected to 'Molecular world and parts' (via 'use to appear in'), 'Samples or Specimen' (via 'exemplifies'), and 'Complex System' (via 'cross reference'). 'Samples or Specimen' is connected to 'collections' (via 'part of') and 'Complex System' (via 'from'). 'Complex System' is connected to 'Time' and 'Place' (via 'occurs in') and 'Situation' (via 'based on'). 'Observations' and 'Simulation' are connected to 'Activities' (via 'create maintain') and 'Situation' (via 'describe'). 'Activities' is also connected to 'Time' and 'Place'. On the left, a vertical stack of boxes includes 'global indices', 'databases', 'Publications', 'mathem. Models', 'Records', and 'Forecasts', with arrows indicating interactions. A large purple oval labeled 'create maintain' is positioned between 'Publications' and 'Records'.</p>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Environment, Observations</p>
<h3 style="text-align: center;">THIST Placement</h3> <p>The diagram illustrates the THIST Placement, which is a modified version of the MOLES Placement. It features a central 'Species (bio,geo)' box with a dashed box around it labeled 'cross reference'. 'Species (bio,geo)' is connected to 'Molecular world and parts' (via 'use to appear in') and 'Samples or Specimen' (via 'exemplifies'). 'Samples or Specimen' is connected to 'collections' (via 'part of') and 'Complex System' (via 'from'). 'Complex System' is connected to 'Time' and 'Place' (via 'occurs in') and 'Situation' (via 'based on'). 'Observations' and 'Simulation' are connected to 'Activities' (via 'create maintain') and 'Situation' (via 'describe'). 'Activities' is also connected to 'Time' and 'Place'. On the left, a vertical stack of boxes includes 'global indices', 'databases', 'Publications', 'mathem. Models', 'Records', and 'Forecasts', with arrows indicating interactions. A large purple oval labeled 'create maintain' is positioned between 'Publications' and 'Records'.</p>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Species</p>

Placement of the model	Comment
<h3 style="text-align: center;">VOID Placement</h3> <p>The diagram illustrates the VOID Placement model. It features a central 'Activities' node with a purple oval labeled 'create maintain' around it. 'Activities' is connected to 'Observations' and 'Simulation'. 'Observations' leads to 'Records' and 'Forecasts', while 'Simulation' leads to 'Forecasts'. 'Activities' also connects to 'Time' and 'Place'. 'Species (bio,geo)' is linked to 'Molecular world and parts' (via 'use to appear in'), 'Collections' (via 'exemplifies'), and 'Samples or Specimen' (via 'cross reference' and 'exemplifies'). 'Samples or Specimen' is linked to 'Complex System' (via 'from') and 'Collections' (via 'part of' and 'from'). 'Complex System' is linked to 'Time' and 'Place' (via 'occurs in') and 'Situation' (via 'based on'). 'Situation' is linked to 'Forecasts' (via 'describe'). 'Publications' is linked to 'databases' and 'global indices' (via 'is about'). 'Molecular world and parts' is linked to 'Services'.</p>	<p><u>Focus:</u> Collections</p>
<h3 style="text-align: center;">Dublin Core and SKOS Placement</h3> <p>This diagram is identical to the VOID Placement diagram above. However, a dashed box encloses the left-side components: 'global indices', 'databases', 'Publications', 'mathem. Models', 'Records', and 'Forecasts'. This indicates that in the Dublin Core and SKOS placement, these components are treated as general domain-independent elements rather than being specifically tied to collections.</p>	<p><u>Focus:</u> General, application domain independent</p>

Figure 10 Placement of the models in the conceptual backbone

3 Requirements and Gaps regarding the Vision of Harmonized Metadata, Semantics and Ontologies

3.1 As Identified by the Related Tasks of SCIDIP-ES

The contents of this section are largely based on the SCIDIP-ES results of the 1st year (D12.1, M9) as well as on 2nd year results (D33.1 and TN-WP33-T33.3, M20).

From SCIDIP-ES Deliverable D12.1 (Requirements Specification and Gap Analysis, M9):

According to the survey performed in D12.1, the majority of users declare that they do not adopt well-known standards for their archives. In particular 67% of the Data Managers and 74% of the Data Producers that participated in the survey do not use any common standard for their data. The rest stated one of the following: ISO 19115, OGC, OAIS, Observation and Measurements (with or without the Earth Observation Profile), SensorML, OAIS.

Furthermore Data Consumers use other information related to digital objects needed for their work. The majority of this information is related to the data structure (70%), provenance (50%), context information (40%), data semantics in general (30%), qualification (30%) and data rendering information (10%).

*The main outcome of the analysis of the requirements survey is that: **Mechanisms to search and find data do not satisfy users: they need to use multiple databases and multiple queries to find the information that they are looking for.** Tools are currently used to perform activities including transformation, access, extraction, visualization, etc. but almost all these tools are bespoke or custom built. An important point which should be considered during the customization of the SCIDIP-ES services and toolkits is that many of the stakeholders have more than one of role in their organizations*

Some conclusions from SCIDIP-ES Deliverable D33.1 (Earth Science Common Policies and Data Access Policies Analysis, M20):

As documented in WP 15, users generally have a better understanding of the discovery and retrieval system used to access the data than the underlying archive service. About data discovery, metadata standards used in Earth Science Domain are ISO 19115, ISO 19119, and Open Archive Protocol for metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH).

- Data Access: Web services are most commonly used for accessing an archive*
- Wide variety of portals currently in use for accessing different data types.*
- Standard used: products: specific for each domain: (i.e. NASA AIM format, NETCDF, etc...)*
- Software: specific for each domain*
- Documentation: pdf, xml*
- Interoperability and file format: common points: use common standard*

The SCIDIP-ES Task 33.3 aims at performing a deep analysis of ES community needs and gaps in terms of available tools and services as well as in terms of interoperability of the current ES infrastructures starting from the user requirements collected in WP 12 and the results of the survey carried out in WP 15. Some results from the corresponding **SCIDIP-ES Deliverable “TN33.1 Earth Science Infrastructures and Gap Analysis”** (March 2013) follow:

That report considered two dimensions which are shown in the next figure (which has been derived from TN33.1 – Earth Science Infrastructure Interoperability and Gap Analysis (due to M20)).

Figure 11 ES data lifecycle in two dimensions

The first dimension concerns the high level functional architectural schema that implicitly characterize the life-cycle of scientific data from its production, publication, storage to its search, use and re-use by the user communities. For reasons of self-containedness it is also given below.

Function	Description
Acquisition/Ingestion	Acquisition describes the complete process from data acquisition from one instrument, data transfer and reception, up to the reconstruction of instrument source packets. The ingestion function accepts data from different sources: data transfer segment reception, processing or data migration elements. It is a process of preparing, indexing, and adding information or data into a managed domain within an information repository or preservation repository. The product is consistently submitted to archiving and cataloguing (eventually).
Archiving	The archiving function includes the supporting processes, policies, hardware and software used to preserve information and data, if required for long-term. This

	function includes all operations to store the data and ensure their integrity.
Processing/ Reprocessing	The processing function generates higher level products from lower level products and auxiliary products. The processing is performed by core algorithms supplemented by administrative functions (e.g. formatting). Processing is capable to produce the desired products systematically or on request. Re-processing is a specialization of processing where a complete product collection is systematically generated to obtain a new revision using archived lower level products.
Packaging	The packaging function provides the conceptual relationships among the various components of the package that describe which data objects are described by which science metadata documents, and the role in that description that they play. The data package concept also provides a consistent mechanism to define one or more serialized representations of a package that can be used to transport the components of a data package from one system to another.
Cataloguing	The cataloguing function provides search and retrieve capabilities for digital objects. It supports data management functionality (e.g. inventory, archiving) based on references to corresponding data products stored by archiving. Products can be organized in collections with restricted access depending on product type and users.
Consumer Interfaces	Consumer interfaces are in charge of interfacing and managing users to interact with the system/ federated archives/services. This functionality comprises: user information (e.g. access to guide, catalogue search and retrieval, ordering, user profiles), user support (e.g. user registration, authentication and authorization), user management (e.g. maintenance users profiles, accounts), user services (e.g. data access, query interfaces).
Multi-domain search/retrieve	The multi-domain search/retrieve function provides search and retrieve capabilities for digital objects in various scientific domain with additional capability for discovering and accessing heterogeneous and federated data and services resources. It supports data management functionality based on references to corresponding data products stored by archiving. The function includes also user information functions comprises access to guide, catalogue search and retrieval, ordering, user profiles and other interface functions for external users.

Table 7 Description of functionalities in the high level functional architecture (from TN33.1)

The second dimension shows the three basic dimension/phases in the Long Term Data Preservation of Earth Science data identified and defined in the D12.1:

- **Archive Definition and Set-up (AD):** including the definition of what ES data and associated information to archive/ how, when, for how long, inventorying of this data and information, cataloguing and archiving.
- **Archive Content Discovery, Access and Processing (DA):** including the ability to allow search and discovery of data and associated information in the archive, to allow users to access, understand and use e.g. and to perform additional processing.
- **Archive Evolution (EV):** ability to support archive evolution in response to changes in Designated Community, technology, policies, etc. Evolution should aim at preserving the information content of the archive (i.e. data and associated information) and at the same time ensuring discoverability and accessibility.

The above functional modeling is certainly useful. However note that the perspective that is probably the more important is the **structural one**.

The structure of information determines what the various functions can do, or cannot do, it also determines the implementation of the functions. This justifies the value of good structural domain modeling.

For example, the following table shows the aforementioned functions and for each one it explains how a solution based on a single conceptual model, implemented using Semantic Web technologies, could be used for tackling the corresponding requirements. This is just an indicative conceptual model. More about candidate conceptual models are being described in the next section.

Function	Implementation assuming a particular ontology
Acquisition/ Ingestion	CRMdig [23] can be used for modelling the context and provenance of the ingested information. Moreover, custom inference rules can also be employed (a) for reducing the manual effort for recording provenance metadata, (b) for reducing the required storage space, and (c) for “completing” the provenance information [44]
Archiving	The information can be archived in RDF/XML as instances of the CRMdig ontology. It can be stored in files, or RDF triplestores. Various methods for compaction have also been proposed for such repositories.
Processing/ Reprocessing	CRMdig allows representing all processing steps and derivation chains (e.g. [23]).
Packaging	CRMdig and semantic web technologies can alleviate the need for “classical” packaging. More details are given on section 4.3.2.
Cataloguing	Search and retrieval capabilities can be supported by the Semantic Web Query Languages and protocols (SPARQL), which can operate over one or more triple-stores (that store the CRMdig-based data). An enrichment CRMdig regarding geospatial capabilities is CRMspatial described in Section 4.2.2
Consumer Interfaces	<i>This aspect is orthogonal to conceptual modeling.</i>
Multi-domain search/retrieve	CRMdig contains a rich structure of classes and properties which are very generic and can be used for multi domain interoperability.

Table 8 An example of supporting the high level functions based on a ontology and Semantic Web technologies

Therefore in this report we focus more on domain modelling and the structural perspective.

3.2 Challenges

Information integration and interoperability is the big challenge. For instance, consider the following scenario:

Suppose that we have measurements about the Arctic Ocean, specifically temperature measurements, ice and sea measurements for a specific location. These have been represented using model A (could be one of the models identified in Section 2.3). However there might be information about the plants and wildlife that exist in this specific location, which are described in another model, say B. If someone wants to get specific information about the fishes that live in a specific range of temperature or ice thickness measurement, then it is necessary to query both these models. It is therefore important that these models could be harmonized (using any of the approaches described later on in Section 4.1) to answer such queries.

We could say that the grand challenge is to realize the **Semantic Web** (or **Web of Data**) vision, i.e. to connect all data/information for forming a kind of Giant Global Graph (GGG) of interconnected data coming from different data sources for allowing the development of intelligent information and content integration services. This vision is described in more detail at Section 4.3.

Another recent and detailed document about current challenges and possible solutions is given in the APARSEN Deliverable D25.1 [36] which provides: an analysis of interoperability issues in digital preservation, an overview of 64 projects and initiatives in different areas of digital preservation, including specific domains like Earth Science and Linked Data, a description and evaluation of **13 interoperability scenarios** and **related challenges**, a matrix of models, standards and services for interoperability (58 rows) grouped according to various criteria (by Digital Preservation areas, interoperability objects and challenges), a gap analysis to diagnose the landscape and identify future actions and goals, plus recommendations and guidelines for decision makers and practitioners. Just indicatively, Figure 12 shows a diagram synopsising the identified solutions grouped in various categories.

Figure 12 A Diagram showing a number of solutions (taken from APARSEN D25.1)

4 Strategy for having Harmonized Metadata, Semantics and Ontologies

In this section we describe which are the possible strategies for having harmonized metadata, semantics and ontologies. In general we can identify two main strategies:

- [S1] Compliance with Standards
- [S2] Adopt Integration/Harmonization approaches

Regarding [S1], there is adequate standardization (mandated) in the geographical domain. Two major standardisation organisations ISO and OGC cooperate together to develop interoperability standards that are increasingly becoming adopted. Adoption in Europe is quickly accelerating due to the entry into force of the INSPIRE directive which mandates the use of these standards. The most important standardised models are:

- ISO1956: Standard that defines the metadata conceptual model required to describe geographic datasets and dataset series (encoding defined in ISO19139).
- ISO19119: Standard that describes the metadata conceptual model required to describe geographic services (encoded is defined in ISO19139).
- ISO19110: Standard that defines the model for describing feature types.
- ISO 19156 using ISO 19109 : Standard that provides a model for describing observations. This model is used as the base for many of the INSPIRE data specifications as well as the Earth Observation Metadata Application Profile of O&M. Features and observations are encoded using ISO19139.

Regarding [S2], the notion and approaches for integration/harmonization are described next.

According to the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative, **metadata harmonization** is defined as «*the ability of two or more systems or components to exchange "combined metadata" conforming to two or more metadata specifications, and to interpret the metadata that has been exchanged in a way that is consistent with the intentions of the creators of the metadata*» and as "**recipe for harmonization**" it states: «*1. Adopt a Core Model with support for machine-processable semantics (i.e., RDF), and 2. Construct mappings of other standards to the Core Model -- mappings which preserve semantics*».

4.1 Integration Approaches

An excerpt from the DoW regarding strategies for having harmonized metadata, semantics and ontologies: *"The strategy could for example consist in the need for a mediator among existing ontologies and in such a case the specifications will be defined in the task and provided as input to Task 21.8 for the implementation activities and for the validation in the ES specific domain"*.

The availability of mapping between various models (metadata schemas/ontologies) is crucial for interoperability. They allow building tools and systems for exchanging and integrating information. Specifically they can be exploited for implementing a *materialized integration*

(warehouse), or a *virtual integration* (mediator) approach. Below we discuss in brief these approaches and refer to tools and system that can exploit such mappings.

Materialized views

Virtual views

Figure 13 Integration Approaches

4.1.1 Materialized Integration

Materialized Integration relies on a central repository where all data are to be stored, called “Data Warehouse” [12]. Mappings are used to extract information from data sources, to transform it to the target model and then to store it at the central repository [8], [14]. It is good practice not to modify extracted information after its transformation except for the use of common identifiers. Rather, any need for updating individual information is covered by requesting source providers to make updated sources available.

There are some important issues that should be taken into account for designing and maintaining a data warehouse. Firstly (designing phase) the information from each source that is going to be used should be selected. Specific views over the sources should be chosen in order to be materialized and the global schema employed by the warehouse should be constructed. Next (maintenance phase) issues should be tackled concerning the warehouse initial population by the source data and the update of the data when sources are refreshed. The most elegant solution to this problem discussed in literature since the 1990ies are the Named Graph or “context” mechanisms in RDF Triple Stores. Finally, there are some query processing, storage and indexing issues that should be taken into consideration.

The great advantage of materialized integration is the great flexibility in transformation logic, decoupling of the release management of the integrated resource from the management cycles of the sources and the decoupling of access load from the source servers

4.1.2 Virtual Integration

On the other hand, Virtual Integration approaches do not rely on a central repository but leave the data in the original sources. Mappings are exploited there to enable query translation from one model to another. Then data from disparate sources are combined and returned to the user.

Early approaches for Virtual Integration were first introduced as “Federated Database Systems” [22] and “Mediation” was later proposed [26]. The mediator (a.k.a. integrator) performs the following actions: First it receives a query formulated in terms of the unified model/schema and decomposes these queries into sub-queries. These queries are addressed to specific data sources. This decomposition is based on the mappings generated between the unified model and the source models, which play an important role in the sub-queries' execution plan optimization. Finally, the sub-queries are sent to the wrappers of the individual sources, which transform them into queries over the sources. The results of these sub-queries are sent back to the mediator. At this point the answers are merged into one and returned to the user. Besides the possibility of asking queries, the mediator has no control over the individual sources.

The great advantage (but in some cases disadvantage) of virtual integration is the real-time reflection of source updates in integrated access. The higher complexity of the system and the quality of service demands on the sources is only justified if immediate access to updates is indeed required.

4.1.3 System and Tools

Several systems employ the aforementioned techniques in order to enable transparent data access to heterogeneous sources. Below we briefly mention some of them:

Generic Mapping/Transformation Tools

At http://www.cidoc-crm.org/crm_mappings.html there are various documents, e.g. [15], that contain information on how to define mappings between relevant data structures and the CIDOC CRM. Furthermore generic data transformation tools (such as *XML2RDF Data Transformation Tool* which maps XML data files to RDF files, given a schema matching definition) are available. Other tools such as [4] are used to define mappings between OWL/RDF and relational models which then can be used in other query/data translation modules. All current mapping tools suffer from the fact that they are either too simplistic for the typical heterogeneity of sources, or schema matching definitions and target identifier generation rules are encoded in a way domain experts of the sources cannot verify. Further, there is virtually no effective support to quickly process schema updates of sources and targets and changes in the identifier policy of the targets.

Atlas

Atlas [21] is a biological data warehouse aimed at bioinformatics doing research in that area. SQL access is possible to each stored databases by creating a relational data model for each of them. Integration is done by cross-referencing protein sequence and gene identifiers.

BACIIS

BACIIS [18] uses a mediator-wrapper architecture augmented with a knowledge base. The wrapper extracts information from a given remote data source and the mediator transforms data from its format in the source database to the internal format used by the integration system. The BACIIS knowledge base has two components: the ontology and the data source schema. The ontology provides a method for mapping differences in terminology to a common term and it is used for syntactic and semantic reconciliation.

MECOTA

MECOTA [25] is a semantic rule-based mediator designed to reconcile structural and semantic heterogeneity. Thus, MECOTA defines the concept of context transformation meaning that “a value has to be considered in its context and may be transformed into another context” by applying two different rules: combination and replacement rules. The first rule constructs new information for structural heterogeneity problems, such as adding desired information from other sources. The second rule transforms information into another structure.

MAFRA

MAFRA [16] stands for Mapping Framework. It is a system for extracting mappings from ontologies and executing them as data transformation from one ontology to another one. The specific framework proposed offers support in all parts of the ontology mapping life-cycle.

Kleisli

Kleisli [6], [27] is a system designed to perform integrated queries across distributed and heterogeneous databases. A federated approach is adopted for integrating biological databases and tools, like BLAST. Its type-inference system makes unnecessary the adoption of a global data model for describing the sources of data, enhancing system flexibility.

TAMBIS

TAMBIS [10] is a database integration system for the molecular biology and bioinformatics area. Developers of TAMBIS focused on offering a high transparency level while allowing users to perform complex queries on the integrated repositories. It adopts a federated approach, using a self-designed ontology, as a global schema.

SEMEDA

SEMEDA [13] is a federated system for semantic integration of biological databases. Users are hidden from the internal structure of data sources. SEMEDA uses a custom ontology containing small top-level biological concepts. Other domain-related ontologies are employed as controlled vocabularies.

DiscoveryLink

DiscoveryLink [11] is a federated system for semantic integration of life science data sources. DiscoveryLink was born from the fusion of the Garlic and the DataJoiner systems. It adopts a wrapper-based architecture, with wrappers dealing with interfacing with the sources, and a middleware engine processing end-user SQL queries.

INDUS

INDUS [5] is an ontology-based system to integrate heterogeneous biological data sources. Users can define their own ontology to reflect their domain view on the underlying data.

OntoFusion

Ontofusion [19] is a system designed to perform integration at the schema level. It is based on ontologies for representing the source schemas and the global schema. Integration is achieved in two steps: first, virtual schemas for each of the sources are constructed. Afterwards, automatic unification of the schemas takes place to build the global schema.

ACGT Semantic Mediator

The European project ACGT included in its tasks the development of a semantic mediation layer for accessing data from clinical trials [17]. It adopted a federated approach, with a wrapper-mediator architecture. An ontology built within the same project, the ACGT Master Ontology, served as global schema. Users could perform SPARQL queries in terms of this ontology to access the underlying sources.

SPARQL-RW

The SPARQL-RW [33] (SPARQL ReWriting) framework provides a transparent query access over mapped RDF datasets. This framework provides a methodology for SPARQL query mediation over federated OWL/RDF knowledge bases. To this end a rich set of mappings, based on Description Logic semantics is supported. The process is the following: The queries sent to the global ontology, are decomposed, rewritten and submitted to the federated sources. They are evaluated and returned back to the mediator.

4.1.4 Mappings

There are various recent reports that provide information about mappings between particular models. Below we list some indicative ones.

For instance one of the outcomes of the W3C incubator group on provenance, was the establishment of mappings between the following models:

- Open Provenance Model
- Provenir ontology
- Provenance Vocabulary
- Proof Markup Language
- Dublin Core
- PREMIS
- WOT Schema
- SWAN Provenance Ontology
- Semantic Web Publishing Vocabulary
- Changeset Vocabulary

The specific mappings and other details are presented at:

http://www.w3.org/2005/Incubator/prov/wiki/Provenance_Vocabulary_Mappings.

The APARSEN NoE, specifically the Deliverable D24.1 [35] (and in more details the internal deliverable ID2401) provides mappings between models for recording and exchanging provenance information. For instance, Open Provenance Model (OPM) and CIDOC CRM_{dig} are good hubs for provenance models (in the sense that there are several mappings of these models to other models as shown in the next figure). In the context of APARSEN a mapping between them has been specified.

Figure 14 Mappings between Provenance Models

4.2 Candidate Core Ontologies

Below we describe two ontologies that have been proposed plus some related suggestions by OGC.

4.2.1 ISO 19100 Series and OGC Specifications

The ISO 19100 series of standards have been the basis for the development of well-known semantic models (including MOLES, GeoSciML and many others). Furthermore ISO is in close cooperation with OGC for the development of emerging standards. The main concern of these standards (ISO 19100 series and OGC Specifications) is to support the interoperability of geoinformation systems which are the building blocks of spatial information infrastructures. For achieving interoperability these standards provide a basic conceptualization of: (a) unified data models, (b) well defined interfaces, (c) languages to access and manipulate data based on these interfaces and (d) automatic translation of data and models.

The well-known ISO 19115 standard provides a structure for describing digital geographic metadata. As stated in [45] it is sufficient for capturing enough of the context surrounding the data, however it cannot be used for capturing other important preservation-related metadata as specified in the OAIS reference model [46], such as Representation Information (RI), or Preservation Description Information (PDI). In [45] a preservation profile of ISO 19115 has been developed, based on the metadata requirements specified in the OAIS reference model. The main purpose of this profile is to enable capturing preservation-related information about geospatial dataset, while persisting the ability to capture contextual metadata of these datasets using the core ISO 19115 model. Figure 15 below shows the base ISO 19115 packages in yellow, and the proposed extensions in white. The extended classes fall in four different categories: Annotation, Provenance, Authenticity and Representation Information.

Figure 15 Preservation Profile for ISO 19115

Annotation provides the creator of the metadata to add descriptive text, providing clarification where felt necessary. To attach annotations with the property they are intended for, the concept of an AnnotationContext has been created as well. **Provenance** is used to track a dataset through its “data life cycle”, capturing information on each transformation that has been performed, such as its date, method, and outcome. This information is necessary for the assessment of a datasets validity and authenticity. To this end, the profile extends two core ISO19115 concepts, *ProcessStep* and *Lineage*. **Representation information** denotes all information required to process, parse and visualize data. In a long-term preservation scheme, this OAIS concept has been created to guarantee future users of data to possess all the tools to be able to read data and understand it, both from a structural as a semantic point of view (i.e. how is the data encrypted, and what does it mean). **Authenticity**, finally, relates to provenance in that it tracks the veracity of the data over time, capturing concepts such as fixity (the data

has not been altered, verifiable using checksums) and digital signatures to prove the data's origin.

Besides the preservation profile, recent work has been shown that there is growing interest in modeling data provenance. In particular [47] describes an architecture of a Web Processing Service capable of conflating two datasets while capturing provenance information about the process. Furthermore it describes how provenance information can be encoded using the ISO 19115 metadata model. The term provenance is understood (in terms of ISO 19115) as the lineage or pedigree. The metadata element for lineage as defined in ISO 19115 (part 2) provides the two main elements *ProcessStep* and *Source*. This rather simple model is sufficient to provide an overview about the processing a dataset originates from (even if detailed capturing of the process is not feasible).

While ISO 19115 is the standard Metadata scheme for geographic datasets, its structure is not the most appropriate when dealing with Earth Observation (EO) products: the required ISO19115 metadata elements like title, abstract, contact point, etc. make the description of EO products less efficient, while important attributes for the description of various EO products are missing. To address this problem, a profile of ISO 19156 called the Earth Observation Metadata profile of Observations and Measurements (OGC 10-157) has been developed in the context of the HMA projects. Similarly to ISO 19115 it provides some elements for capturing preservation related information. For example provenance information can be encoded in the acquisition and processing information data structures, However authenticity, annotation and representation information could be better expressed. The development of a preservation extension on top of OGC 10-157 would be useful. Work is currently being undertaken in this area by mapping the metadata defined in the ESA SAFE format to OGC10-157 and creating a specific extension of OGC10=157 to capture the metadata elements that are missing.

4.2.2 CIDOC CRM with extensions

The CIDOC CRM (ISO21127) [3] provides the concepts to model the complexity of cultural heritage and archaeological data in their semantic context, but also scientific observation, measurement and processing activities. For example the showing figure shows an example over ESA Earth Observation Data. Specifically it shows how the transformation of L0 → L1 → L2 products can be modelled

SCIDIP-ES
Science Data Infrastructure for Preservation – Earth Science

Figure 16 Example of using ISO21127 for documenting the transformation L0 → ... → L2 products

Its spatial concepts have been designed to interface with OGC standards for further refinement.

Recent research at FORTH²⁰ however has revealed that CIDOC CRM and OGC standards are opaque with respect to the exact relationship of the real extent of the matter of features to given geometries. As a consequence, both standards fail at scale-independent integration of geometric data with data of other semantics. For instance, the given geometry of a detail of a borehole for water sampling may not overlap with the given geometry of the borehole as a whole (see hydrological definitions in INSPIRE). This problem is particularly important for integration of archaeological excavation and find data and historical references, but also in other sciences.

In order to solve this problem, current research at FORTH has been producing a novel “articulation” of the CIDOC CRM with OGC standards, i.e. a common ontological refinement of both standards capable to explain the missing details as specializations of both models simultaneously. The resulting model, which for the moment is called CRMgeo, will be a spatiotemporal extension to the CIDOC CRM expressed in RDF. CRMgeo integrates the CRM with the OGC standard of GeoSPARQL [32], [33] and thus provides the concepts to represent current standardised geo-information in an ontological network with its data, metadata and provenance data.

²⁰ Research not funded by SCIDIP-ES

The benefits stemming from such a model is that one could use it for building repositories that host both spatial data and other semantic resources. Moreover, it could be exploited as the schema for information integration, either in a materialized approach, or a virtual approach (recall section 5.1). The basic service over an integrated repository is the search/query service. To this end we should mention at this point GeoSPARQL.

Such models are the basic ones for communities that want to share their geospatial content in the web, e.g. as Linked Data. During the last years OGC Standards have evolved to capture the “links” between several different concepts. Some indicative types of such links are parameters, features, units, sensor types etc. Furthermore each candidate OGC service or encoding standard, which is being developed through the OGC Interoperability Program,²¹ is being designed with the Semantic Web principles in mind. To this end OGC Naming Authority subcommittee has been created with the responsibility of managing the URIs given in several concepts. A more detailed description of the basic principles of Linked Data can be found at Section 4.3.

In comparison to OGC Abstract Specifications (AS), we could say that OGC AS is not at the same level as the CRM. OGC AS are defined in UML with attributes, therefore they cannot provide the same semantic representation and integration capabilities as an ontology purely based on classes and properties with a property hierarchy. Another difference of CRM and ISO 19156 is the event centric nature of CRM providing integration possibilities not available in ISO 19156 or ISO 19115.

4.3 Semantic Web Technologies and Linked Data

We should also stress that RDF/S is currently the lingua franca for metadata and semantic descriptions. The adoption of this representation framework has various benefits (exploitation of the tools that have been developed, Linked Data initiative, etc).

Below we analyze this approach (the material was largely based on the APARSEN Deliverable D25.1 “Interoperability Objectives and Approaches”).

There has been a growing interest and application of the W3C²² standards to enable semantic web-scale interoperability. Recently, several parties (digital preservation communities, cultural heritage data providers) have also started to manifest a positive attitude toward this approach [39], despite an initial scepticism and some criticisms. Indeed a growing number of initiatives are now adopting the Semantic Web technologies to address some digital preservation issues, like accessibility, access, intelligibility and semantics, searching, annotation, harmonization, integration, contextualization.

According to the W3C definition, the Semantic Web is a collaborative effort, which “provides a common framework that allows data to be shared and reused across application, enterprise and community boundaries.” The vision is based on the idea of extending the principles of the

²¹ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/ogc/programs/ip>

²² <http://www.w3.org>

Web from documents to data by defining and describing the relations among data on the Web. These meaningful relationships can be established between any named resources in the Web documents by enabling an automatic integration of data.

The Semantic Web architecture is illustrated by the Semantic Web Stack, also known as Semantic Web Cake or Semantic Web Layer Cake. It is a kind of layered architecture for interoperability; standardization on one level allows standardizing an upper level and so on. For instance standardizing the structure (e.g. XML) allows standardizing structure queries (e.g. XQuery). Such stacks can be conceived as a kind of layered interoperability objectives, which also show the standards used for meeting these objectives in order to achieve the full Semantic Web vision. The stack is still evolving and it is still not clear how the top of the stack will be realized.

Figure 17 The stack of Semantic Web technologies

A more detailed figure follows which also shows the Linked Open Data, which is described next. The figure shows that the Linked Data Approach adopts a small fraction of the Semantic Web technologies. For the purpose of this document, we use the term “Semantic Web” to refer to the full suite of W3C standards including XML, RDF, SPARQL, query language, and OWL ontology language and so on.

Figure 18 Semantic Web technologies and Linked Data

As shown in Figure 18, the Linked Data approach lies at the core of the Semantic Web stack by adopting a small selection of semantic web technologies. This approach was started as a way of enabling the creation of a **web of data** (a global information space of interlinked datasets, as represented by the Linked Data Cloud in Figure 19, which has the potential to reproduce the network effect that the web of documents had on hypertexts making easier to reuse and combine data on the Web. The rationale behind this approach is that linking data distributed across the Web requires a standard mechanism for describing the existence and meaning of links between the entities named in this data. There are already billions of RDF triples which have been published according to the principles of Linked Data and are publicly available.

Figure 19 Linked Data Cloud

This idea is summarized by a set of best practices, introduced by Tim Berners-Lee in [41] for publishing and interlinking structured data on the Web:

1. Use URIs as names of things.
2. Use HTTP URIs so that people can look up those names.
3. When someone looks up a URI, provide useful information, using the standards (RDF*, SPARQL).
4. Include links to other URIs, so that they can discover more things.

The first principle states that URIs, and more specifically HTTP URIs, should be used as a globally unique identification mechanism to name and describe any entity on the Web (not only digital objects but also real world objects and abstract concepts). According to the second principle, the use of HTTP URIs is recommended to enable the resolution of the URIs, over the HTTP protocol, into a description of the identified entities. The key advantage of HTTP URIs is that they can be directly looked up through a pervasive protocol, HTTP, without adding any resolvers or levels of indirection. The third best practice advocates the use of a standard mechanism for publishing structured data on the Web, i.e. the Resource Description Framework (RDF) and a standard language for querying these data, i.e. SPARQL. Finally, the fourth principle, recommends the use of hyperlinks (i.e. RDF links) to connect things and describe relationships between them. RDF links connect distributed data into a single global information space enabling applications to navigate this space and retrieve integrated information about the described entities. The idea is that by representing contents in standardized highly structured formats like RDF, machines can “understand” the meaning of

these contents. This would allow the implementation of more sophisticated services, like for services for information searching, which may provide more accurate search results.

In summary, we can state that the Linked Data vision is built upon two simple ideas:

1. To employ the RDF data model to publish structured data on the Web;
2. To use http URIs to describe the properties and relationships between data items across data sources.

Based on this definition, we can conceive the Linked Data principle as an enabling factor for realizing the global web of structured data, which is part of the Semantic Web vision. The key idea of the approach is that the different parts of the resulting Giant Global Graph (GGG) of interconnected data can come from different data sources by allowing the development of intelligent information and content integration services.

According to many, Linked Data seems to offer a valid approach to address many of the interoperability issues faced in digital preservation providing solutions for data search, virtualisation and integration. In the domain of cultural heritage, for example, Semantic Web technologies have been proposed as a promising approach for making multi-format, multi-topical, multi-lingual, multi-cultural and multi-target content mutually interoperable (at syntactic but especially at semantic and organizational levels) so that it can be searched, linked and published in a harmonized way across the boundaries of the datasets and data silos [39].

It is interesting to note the emergence and increasing adoption of RDFa (standing for “Resource Description Framework – in – attributes”). It is a W3C Recommendation that adds a set of attribute-level extensions to HTML, XHTML and various XML-based document types for embedding rich metadata within Web documents. The RDF data-model mapping enables its use for embedding RDF subject-predicate-object expressions within XHTML documents. It also enables the extraction of RDF model triples by compliant user agents. There are popular CMSs that already support RDFa, and this trend can have significant impact on the linking of documents (e.g. web pages) with data (linked data).

To encourage users adopt the Linked Data principles W3C announced the 5-Star-Linked-Data [63] initiative as a best practice for publishing Linked Data. It is a rating system, which allows users ensuring that their data are open-accessible and interlinked.

Figure 20 Ranking of Open Data (taken from 5stardata.info)

The lowest rating (1 star) is given for datasets which are available on the web (in any format), but with an open license (e.g. a pdf document showing temperature measurements). 2 stars are given for datasets which are accessible on the web in a structured machine-readable format, so anyone can re-use them (e.g. an XLS file with temperature measurements). 3 stars are given to datasets which do not depend on proprietary software (e.g. use CSV instead of XLS). 4 stars are given to datasets which are in the web in the sense that they contain URIs (an RDFa file, so that other resources can point to them). The highest rating (5 stars) is given to data which are linked with other data to provide a description of the context (an RDFa with properties linking to other Linked Data).

However, by creating widely-distributed, highly-volatile and largely-integrated streams of data, the Linked Data approach challenges existing paradigms of data sharing and raises the need to re-think provenance and authenticity solutions. For others, Linked Data has some crucial limitations that make its implementation and use in many contexts very challenging (or even not feasible). A raised problem concerns the maturity and scalability of Linked Data technologies, which can represent an obstacle for digital preservation that deals with high volumes of data and metadata and has strong persistence requirements. However Linked Data can be used as a publishing space. They are not proposed as a replacement of the operational databases of data/metadata. Indeed several tools that carry out the task of producing and publishing linked data from databases have been emerged.

The lack of vocabularies to describe a lot of needed preservation metadata is another mentioned issue by the opponents of the Linked Data approach, even though some solutions

are now available such as OAI-ORE to describe the structure of complex objects (i.e. aggregations of Web resources), the PREMIS Data Dictionary for preservation metadata, preservation vocabularies promulgated by the Library of Congress, etc. Another aspect concerns intellectual property rights and legal issues. Some data in digital preservation institutions like libraries or archives has restricted usage based on local policies, contracts and conditions and rights issues may vary significantly from country to country. Data ownership and rights issues may therefore hinder the release of these data as Linked Open Data. However, the principles of Linked Open Data are also useful for confidential data. For instance, there is the option of Closed Linked Data²³: the application of the linked data techniques on confidential data can be useful for linking these data with other data (either confidential or public), and for specifying the context of these data, e.g. there might be some earth observation data which are not publicly available, however such datasets might be connected to publicly available documents and datasets describing information about the mission, the instruments used, etc.

4.3.1 Semantic Annotations in OGC Standards

The mission of Open Geospatial Consortium²⁴ is to develop standards that enable interoperability and seamless integration of geospatial information, geoprocessing software and geospatial services. Although OGC standards cover the functional dimension of web services they lack to describe their thematic dimensions; OGC standards are not sufficient to describe semantic information. For example OGC standards provide the mechanisms to achieve the syntactic and structural interoperability between different software agents, however it is assumed that these agents have already agreed on how to use these data.

The work on OGC Semantic Annotations [37] tackles the aforementioned problem and proposes three different levels where semantic annotation can be applied; (a) on service metadata, (b) on data models and (c) on data entities. It does not support a new standard, it rather propose extending the notion of already existing OGC standards. Towards this direction it analyzes how the various OGC standards may be affected.

4.3.2 A comparative Example

To make some aspects of the above discussion more clear, below we describe an example with scientific data how different technologies can be used for tackling the needs of preservation and interoperability. The example is based on [42] and [43].

Scenario: *Suppose we want to preserve digital files in ASCII containing temperature measurements from various places on earth. Each file comprises an arbitrary number of lines where each line contains three numerical values: longitude, latitude and measured temperature (in Celsius degrees). Each line corresponds to the temperature at the coordinate-specified area as it was measured at a certain point in time. The time of measurement is*

²³ http://openorg.ecs.soton.ac.uk/wiki/Linked_Data_Basics_for_Techies

²⁴ <http://www.opengeospatial.org/>

hardwired in the name of the file, e.g. a file named **datafile20080903 12PM.txt** contains measurements taken at 12pm of the 3rd September of 2008.

Figure 21 Example of scientific data

Below we shall present in brief two approaches:

- One based on EAST, DEDSL and XFDU that follows the approach: *syntax description* → *semantics description* → *packaging*
- An approach based on “Semantic Web technologies.

4.3.2.1 An approach based on EAST, DEDSL, XFDU

Describing the Syntax

To preserve the **structure** of the file datafile20080903 12PM.txt we could make use of the **EAST (Enhanced Ada SubseT)** language.

Each *Data Description Record* (DDR), according to that language, consists of two packages,

- one for the **logical** description
 - It includes a logical description of all the described components, their size in bits as well as their location within the set of the described data.
- one for the **physical** description
 - It includes a representation of some basic types defined in the logical description and depend on the machine that generates these data: the organization of arrays (i.e. first-index-first, last-index-first) and the bit organization on the medium (high-order-first or low-order-first for big-endian or little-endian representation respectively).

These two packages are mandatory even if the content of the physical part is empty.

An example of a DDR describing datafileX.txt follows:

```
package logical_datafileX_description is

type HORIZONTAL_COORDINATE is range -90.00 .. 90.00
for HORIZONTAL_COORDINATE'size 64; --bits

type VERTICAL_COORDINATE is range -180.00 .. 180.00
for VERTICAL_COORDINATE'size 64;

type TEMPERATURE_TYPE is range -100.0 .. 200.0
for TEMPERATURE_TYPE'size 16;

type MEASUREMENT_TUPLE is record
  LONGITUDE:VERTICAL_COORDINATE
  LATITUDE:HORIZONTAL_COORDINATE
  MEASURED_TEMPERATURE:TEMPERATURE_TYPE
end record;
for MEASUREMENT_TUPLE'size use 144;

type MEASUREMENT_BLOCK is array(1..1000) of MEASUREMENT_TUPLE;
for MEASUREMENT_BLOCK'size use 144000;

SOURCE_DATA:MEASUREMENT_BLOCK

end logical_datafileX_description;

package physical_datafileX_description is

end physical_datafileX_description;
```

Figure 22 Example of an EAST description

We defined three different types one for each column of a data file (longitude, latitude, temperature), since each column represents a different kind of data. The distinction of longitude and latitude is only made because of their different upper and lower bounds.

Describing the Semantics

We can define semantic descriptions for the entities (longitude, latitude and temperature) of the file datafileX.txt aiming at preserving the *meaning* (clarifying the interpretation) of the terms “longitude” “latitude” and “temperature”.

One approach is to use the **DEDSL (Data Entity Dictionary Specification Language)** language. We will see an example of a DEDSL description for datafileX.txt according to the **implementation of DEDSL using XML**.

Note: If we have another file with the same kind of information, we could reuse the same semantic descriptions. So semantic descriptions can be considered as reusable modules. These modules can contain abstract data descriptions to which concrete descriptions may refer.

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding=="UTF-8"?>

<DATA_ENTITY_DICTIONARY>
  <DICTIONARY_IDENTIFICATION>
    <DICTIONARY_NAME CASE_SENSITIVITY="NOT_CASE_SENSITIVE">datafilex Dictionary
    </DICTIONARY_NAME>
  </DICTIONARY_IDENTIFICATION>

  <DATA_ENTITY_DEFINITION CLASS="DATA_FIELD" NAME="LONGITUDE">
    <DEFINITIONAL_PART>
      <DEFINITION>
        It represents the longitude for some certain coordinates. Longitudes east of
        Greenwich shall be designated by the use of plus (+) symbol while longitudes
        west of Greenwich shall be designated with the use of minus (-) symbol.
      </DEFINITION>
      <SHORT_DEFINITION>Longitude</SHORT_DEFINITION>
      <UNITS>deg</UNITS>
    </DEFINITIONAL_PART>
    <REPRESENTATIONAL_PART DATA_TYPE="REAL">
      <RANGE MIN="-180.00" MAX="+180.00"/>
    </REPRESENTATIONAL_PART>
  </DATA_ENTITY_DEFINITION>
  <DATA_ENTITY_DEFINITION CLASS="DATA_FIELD" NAME="LATITUDE">
    <DEFINITIONAL_PART>
      <DEFINITION>
        It represents the latitude for some certain coordinates. Latitudes north of the
        Equator shall be designated by the use of plus (+) symbol while latitudes south
        of the Equator will be designated by the use of minus (-) symbol.
      </DEFINITION>
      <SHORT_DEFINITION>Latitude</SHORT_DEFINITION>
      <UNITS>deg</UNITS>
    </DEFINITIONAL_PART>
    <REPRESENTATIONAL_PART DATA_TYPE="REAL">
      <RANGE MIN="-90.00" MAX="+90.00"/>
    </REPRESENTATIONAL_PART>
  </DATA_ENTITY_DEFINITION>
  <DATA_ENTITY_DEFINITION CLASS="DATA_FIELD" NAME="TEMPERATURE">
    <DEFINITIONAL_PART>
      <DEFINITION>
        It represents the temperature in the area with the specific coordinates.
      </DEFINITION>
      <SHORT_DEFINITION>Temperature</SHORT_DEFINITION>
      <UNITS>Celsius degrees</UNITS>
    </DEFINITIONAL_PART>
    <REPRESENTATIONAL_PART DATA_TYPE="REAL">
      <RANGE MIN="-100.0" MAX="200.0"/>
    </REPRESENTATIONAL_PART>
  </DATA_ENTITY_DEFINITION>
</DATA_ENTITY_DICTIONARY>
```

Figure 23 Example of a DEDSL description

Packaging

Now suppose that we want to preserve and archive a number of datafiles with such measurements. Packaging formats can be used for preparing a package that contains the data files **plus** their EAST and DEDSL descriptions.

We can satisfy such packaging requirements using **XFDU (XML Formated Data Unit (XFDU))** which is a standard file format developed by CCSDS (Consultative Committee for Space Data Systems) for packaging and conveying scientific data, aiming at facilitating information transfer and archiving. The benefit of adopting a packaging approach (like that of XFDU) is that we can also add various information about the components of the package.

For example suppose we would like to include information about the user that took the temperatures for each file, as well as the GPS (Global Positioning System) and the thermometer characteristics or the satellite information (if the samplings were made from space). We can easily add the above information using XFDU since we just have to add the necessary information in the package. For instance, we could describe such information using CIDOC CRM ontology. Such descriptions could be expressed in XML format or as an RDF/XML file (the RDF-case will be described later on). In both cases the file could be included in the package.

It is obvious that the major benefit from the use of XFDU is that we can package together heterogeneous modules (java programs, data-files, GPS info, provenance data) and deliver them to the user, or archive them, as a single (ideally self-describing) unit.

4.3.2.2 An approach based on Semantic Web Technologies

Here we describe an alternative approach that relies on Semantic Web (SW) languages.

In this approach an ontology can be used to describe (syntactically and semantically) the form of the data and ontology-based descriptions can instantiate this ontology. These instantiations are actually the data themselves.

An indicative ontology for our running example expressed in RDF/S XML:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<rdf:RDF xml:lang="en"
  xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
  xmlns:rdfs="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#"
  xmlns:owl="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#"
  xml:base="http://www.ics.forth.gr/is1/temperaturesampling#">

  <rdfs:Class rdf:ID="Sample"/>
  <rdfs:Class rdf:ID="Temperature"/>
  <rdf:Property rdf:ID="hasTemperature">
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="#Sample"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="#Temperature"/>
    <owl:equivalentClass rdf:resource="http://dbpedia.org/resource/Temperature"/>
  </rdf:Property>
  <rdf:Property rdf:ID="celsius">
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="#Temperature"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3c.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal"/>
  </rdf:Property>
  <rdf:Property rdf:ID="hasLongitude">
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="#Sample"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3c.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal"/>
    <owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/wgs84_pos#long"/>
  </rdf:Property>
  <rdf:Property rdf:ID="hasLatitude">
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="#Sample"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3c.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#Literal"/>
    <owl:equivalentProperty rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/wgs84_pos#lat"/>
  </rdf:Property>
</rdf:RDF>
```

Figure 24 RDFS Ontology

The contents of the data files expressed with respect to the ontology (in RDF/S XML):

```
<tmp:sample rdf:about="samplingId_20130314_12PM_35.305_25.072">
  <tmp:hasTemperature>
    <tmp:Temperature>
      <tmp:celsius="25.2"/>
    </tmp:Temperature>
  </tmp:hasTemperature>
  <tmp:hasLongitude="25.072"/>
  <tmp:hasLatitude="35.305"/>
</tmp:sample>
```

Figure 25 Ontology-based descriptions in RDF/XML

Some **benefits** of the SW languages (like RDF/S)

- **The ontology is enough.** When creating a new data file there is no need to create its DEDSL or EAST description every time. Instead we have to represent the data using the syntax specified by the ontology.
- **Evolution.** Whenever we want to preserve more data types we can extend that ontology.
 - For example, past data files can contain only the longitude, the latitude and the temperature, while current ones may contain also the name of each location, or the thermometer used for the measurement. In such cases two different kinds of DEDSL/EAST descriptions have to be created and used. In the SW approach, we just have to extend the top ontology.

Tightly Coupled Descriptions. In SW languages data and their descriptions are tightly coupled. In contrast, EAST/DEDSL-descriptions are represented as separate files and for this reason packaging formats are important. On the other hand in RDF a data file would itself define the data type of each data element in the file. To clarify this point, consider the following line from our running example: 25.130 35.325 30.2. This line does not provide any information regarding what 25.130 might be, it could be either the longitude, or the latitude, or the temperature. On the other hand its RDF representation, as shown in Figure 25, can be easily understood without the existence of any other (EAST/DEDSL) file (e.g. `<tmp:hasLongitude="25.072"/>` clearly denotes the longitude of the area where the temperature sampling was taken).

In brief, the benefits of adopting SW technologies is that they provide standard and semantically interpretable exchange formats, and that the knowledge artifacts expressed in these languages lend themselves to reuse and extension.

5-Star-Linked-Data: The example containing temperatures in various locations expressed in RDF can be rated with 5 stars since the data are expressed in an open format, URIs are being used for identifying the resources and there are links to other Linked Data (e.g. the property `hasLongitude` is equivalent to `http://www.w3.org/2003/01/geo/wgs84_pos#long`). In contrary a dataset described according to (the combination of) EAST, DEDSL, XFDU can be rated with at

most 3 stars. It cannot be rated with 4 stars because these corresponding formats do not use URIs for describing their data, however we should mention that they fulfill some of the requirements for having 5 stars since they describe the context (However they do not use linked data for describing it).

4.4 OGC Core and Extension Mechanism in Earth Science

OGC modular specification [48] proposes a core and extension mechanism to enhance interoperability and harmony between disparate implementations in ES. The core specifies the basic requirements while extensions to the core will define extensions to meet additional requirements. For example, OGC Web Coverage Service (WCS) 2.0 standard provides a scalable solution to support multi-dimensional data/metadata retrieval in unified coverage model. The WCS Core establishes basic spatial and temporal extraction. A set of extensions for defining additional functionality, allows expanding server functionality by following coherent data and service models. Domain-specific metadata, semantics and ontologies can be specified as extensions based on the core model. Specifically, these can be done by the virtualization/mapping/integration of domain concepts to coverage model. For example, Earth Observation (EO) model can be added to the coverage model to construct EO coverage model. Ad-hoc manipulation language, e.g. Web Coverage Processing Language, adds the extra analytic capability to probe earth phenomena in pixel level. A similar approach has been adopted by OpenSearch²⁵, for example a geospatial extension is proposed [49] to specify a series of parameters that can be used to geographically constrain search results. In addition OpenSearch extensions for temporal search and Earth Observation date are currently being developed at OGC.

²⁵ <http://www.opensearch.org>

5 Synopsis and Closing Remarks

Earth science communities use various metadata schemas, to describe different kinds of datasets and for different reasons, and there is not an integrated (harmonized) schema or ontology for describing all concepts of Earth science.

At first this deliverable provided an analysis of the WP15 results (1st year of SCIDIP-ES) with focus on the part of the survey that concerns metadata, semantics and ontologies. It provided an analysis of the semantic models that are widely used by different communities, in terms of their usability, adoption, configurability, and extensibility across different Earth Science domains. A semantic backbone was described comprising fundamental categories and relationships, providing a kind of high level picture of the relationships between human activities and their targets, as they appear on the highest level of description of all scientific products and services. It is only on a more specialized level that all the entities in these models are refined by specific, open-ended terminologies (typologies, taxonomies) and a relatively small set of more specific relationships among them. In the sequel, the placement of the various semantic models in that semantic backbone was described.

Next, the deliverable used the results of the user requirements (WP12), as well as the results of other SCIDIP-ES tasks (i.e. those derived TN33.1), as a pivot for identifying if the aforementioned models/ontologies cover the needs of communities, and for identifying challenges.

The results of the above two parts were used for proposing strategies to have harmonized metadata, semantics and ontologies able to satisfy the user needs coping with the different Earth Science domain approaches. In general, one approach is to comply with standards and we have seen that there is adequate standardization in the geographical domain through the ISO and OGC suite of standards which are the basis for the INSPIRE implementations and hence mandated. The second strategy is to adopt integration/harmonization approaches which rely on mappings. For this reason we described the main approaches for integration/harmonization, we provided a list of tools that can aid such tasks, and provided links to resources that provide particular mappings.

This deliverable also stressed the potential of the Semantic Web and Linked Data trend, supported by an example. Linked Data seems to offer a valid approach to address many of the interoperability issues faced in digital preservation providing solutions for data search, virtualization and integration. For instance, in the domain of cultural heritage, Semantic Web technologies have been proposed as a promising approach for making multi-format, multi-topical, multi-lingual, multi-cultural and multi-target content mutually interoperable (at syntactic but especially at semantic and organizational levels) so that it can be searched, linked and published in a harmonized way across the boundaries of the datasets and data silos [38]. This approach is consistent with the standardization and the integration/harmonization strategy, and gives emphasis on identification, linking, and openness.

The results of this deliverable will be provided as input in T21.8 (Finding Aids Toolkit Development). Some basic recommendations have also been provided in the appendix, while a more detailed set of recommendations are described in a project-internal document.

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Annex C. Terminology

ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
AIP	Archival Information Package
APARSEN	Alliance Permanent Access to the Records of Science in Europe Network
API	Application Programming Interface
CASPAR	Cultural, Artistic and Scientific Knowledge for Preservation, Access and Retrieval
CEDA	Centre for Environmental Data Archival
CIDOC CRM	CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model
CF	Climate and Forecast
CGI	Commission for the management of Geoscience Information
CSML	Climate Science Modeling Language
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
DC	Dublin Core
DEDSL	Data Entity Dictionary Specification Language
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DoW	Description of Work
EAST	Enhanced Ada Subse T
EEA	European Environment Agency
EO	Earth Observation
ES	Earth Science
ETS/CDS	European Topic Centre on Catalogue of Data Sources
FA	Finding Aids
GEMET	General Multilingual Environmental Thesaurus
GENESI-DEC	Ground European Network for Earth Science Interoperations – Digital Earth Communities
GeoSciML	GeoScience Markup Language
GMES	Global Monitoring for Environment and Technology
GML	Geography Markup Language
GSCDA	GMES Space Component Data Access
HMA	Heterogeneous Missions Accessibility
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol Secure
INSPIRE	INfrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IUGS	International Union of Geological Sciences
KB	Knowledge Base
MLT	MultiLingual Thesaurus
MOIST	Multidisciplinary Oceanic Information System
MOLES	Metadata Object for Linking Environmental Sources
MTG	Multilingual Thesaurus of Geosciences
NAL	National Agricultural Library

NetCDF	Network Common Data Form
O&M	Observations and Measurements
OAIS	Open Archival Information System
OAI-ORE	Open Archives Initiative Object Reuse and Exchange
OCL	Object Constraint Language
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OPM	Open Provenance Model
OTEG	Open Access Ontology/ Terminology for the GMES Space Component
OWL	Web Ontology Language
OWS	OGC Web Services
PDI	Preservation Description Information
RDF/S	Resource Description Framework / Schema
RI	Representation Information
RPC	Remote Procedure Call
SCIDIP-ES	Science Data Infrastructure for Preservation – Earth Science
SDI	Spatial Data Infrastructures
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organization System
SPARQL	Simple Protocol and RDF Query Language
SQL	Structured Query Language
SW	Semantic Web
SWE	Sensor Web Enablement
SWEET	Semantic Web for Earth and Environmental Terminology
ThIST	Thesaurus Italiano di Scienze della Terra
TML	Transducer Markup Language
TN	Technical Note
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
UML	Unified Modeling Language
VoID	Vocabulary of Interlinked Datasets
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WCPS	Web Coverage Processing Software
WCS	Web Coverage Service
WFS	Web Feature Service
WKB	Well-Known Binary
WKT	Well-Known Text
WMS	Web Map Service
WMSI	Web Map Server Interface
WP	Work Package
WPS	Web Processing Service
XFDU	XML Formated Data Unit
XML	eXtensible Mark-up Language

Table 9 Terminology

Annex D. Harmonization and SCIDIP-ES Finding Aids (FA) Toolkit

Since one of the main “consumers” of this report is the Finding Aids Toolkit (FA), here we provide a few basic recommendations. A more detailed internal report has been prepared in collaboration with the partners responsible for FA.

D.1. FA: Short Description

The Finding Aids (FA) Toolkit is planned to be based on the ENVRI portal (which in turn is based on GENESI-DEC). The following figure shows the architecture of the current prototype in the form of a UML deployment & component diagram.

Figure 26 The deployment diagram of Finding Aids Toolkit – ENVRI portal

D.2. Recommendations

General recommendations and a list of tools for having harmonized metadata and ontologies were suggested already in **Section 4**. The table that follows lists some additional recommendations that could be useful for FA. Some of the rows concern the ability of FA to behave as a general purpose search/integration toolkit/service, while other rows concern the ability of FA on searching/integrating preservation-related information.

Num	About	Description
R1	Search Services: Query Rewriting for supporting a virtual integration approach	Core ontologies can be used for supporting a kind of very basic inference, allowing users and services to formulate their queries in abstract terms, specifically according to generic core schemas. The mappings between such schemas and the more detailed (or application specific ones), could be exploited (automatically) for obtaining the right answers. → Therefore the provision of a Query Rewriting Module that exploits mappings, should be investigated (various such tools were described

		in this document)
R2	Search Services: Query Expansion using thesauri and controlled vocabularies.	The available structured knowledge can be exploited for tackling the problem of low retrieval effectiveness. The retrieval effectiveness can be low because of various reasons, e.g. multilinguality, language polysemy and homonymy. Thesauri and controlled vocabularies can alleviate this problem.
R3	Semantics- based improvements at various levels	A useful and interesting OGC document that describes semantic annotation is [37]. That document provides various useful recommendations that can be exploited for improving findability and access services.
R4	Browsing Services for Complex Structures	The navigation of structured information, including RepInfo networks, should be flexible even if these networks are complex. The interaction paradigm of Dynamic Taxonomies of Faceted search [38] can alleviate the complexity. Extensions of the model for capturing RDF/S (that allow formulating complex path expressions with simple clicks), or even Fuzzy extensions of RDF/S, have already been specified in the literature[40].

Table 10 Additional Recommendations for FA